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ABSTRACTS

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Could luminescence signals in dune sand be sufficiently bleached?

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The choice of different dating grain-size fractions is an important question for Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL) dating, because different grain-size fractions might have experienced different transporting history and so as to have different bleaching extent. However, aeolian sediments are usually thought to have been well bleached before buried, and most grain-size fractions between 4 μm to 250 μm are usually used for OSL dating. The Qaidam Basin (QB) is an important region for aeolian geomorphologic studies, and OSL dating showed the linear dunes in the central QB were accumulated at 3.0-0.8 ka based on fine grain quartz [1]. To reveal the origin of these linear dunes, detailed OSL dating study were conducted with both coarse grain (150-180 μm) quartz and k-feldspar (KF). However, our BSL and fading-corrected IRSL ages based on coarse grains were all much younger than the former published fine grain BSL ages [1]. For example, some samples dated to ca. 3 ka by fine grains quartz were only dated to ca. 0.3-0.4 ka by coarse grain KF. This obvious difference might be caused by insufficient bleaching of the fine grain sediments. To reveal the bleaching (i.e., residual dose) of different grain-size fractions (4-11, 11-38, 38-63, 63-90, 90-125, 125-150, and 150-180 μm), six modern samples were taken from both linear dunes and barchan dunes in Qarhan Salt Lake region.

D_e s from quartz BSL, KF IRSL₅₀ and post-IR₅₀ IRSL₂₂₅ (pIRIR₂₂₅) were compared on each fraction of 4-11, 11-38, 38-63, 63-90, 90-125, 125-150, and 150-180 μm , respectively. The quartz BSL signals are the easiest to be bleached, while the KF pIRIR₂₂₅ signals the most difficult, so no residual pIRIR₂₂₅ signals indicate the sediments are sufficiently bleached. The results show that: ① KF (pIRIR₂₂₅) of >90 μm fractions could be well bleached, and quartz of >38 μm could be well bleached with ignorable residual dose; ② The fine grain (4-11 μm) sediments were poorly bleached, even the residual age of quartz could be nearly 3 ka, and residual ages of pIRIR₂₂₅ are about 5.5 ka with the highest values of over 25 ka for some aliquots .

This study indicates that even for the dune sand, OSL signals of the fine and medium grain-size fractions might be difficult to be sufficiently bleached, which could cause severely overestimation, especially for the Holocene samples. This might be because the finer grains are more likely to be transported as aggregates (or they are difficult to be deposited on dunes synchronously with coarse grains), and additionally, these fine grain aggregates were mainly eroded from the nearby old yardangs, i.e., short distance transport. As a result, the coarse grain-size sediments might be more suitable for OSL dating in most cases, and sources of sediments should be analysed as well.

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Trapped charge mechanisms' correlation in BeO dosimeter

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Beryllium oxide (BeO hereafter) has been used as a radiation detector due to its properties such as linear dose response, near tissue equivalence, low fading and high sensitivity to radiation dose. The traps of this dosimeter can be stimulated using both thermal and optical stimulation. BeO yields three thermoluminescence (TL hereafter) peaks at 55°C, 192°C, 308°C (at heating rate 1 °C/s), with that at 192°C peak being the main dosimetric peak. The light sensitivity of TL signal makes its usage as a TL dosimeter difficult; however, this feature has led to a potential use as an optically stimulated luminescence (OSL hereafter) detector. The OSL of BeO consists of at least two components and yields two emission bands at ~310 nm and ~370 nm, with the latter being the dominant in OSL emission band. In the present work, the defect centres of BeO were studied with electron spin resonance (ESR) spectroscopy at room temperature. ESR analysis indicated the presence of two defect centres, which were identified as an Al⁺² centre and O⁻ ion. The relationship between these two centres, the corresponding TL traps and the OSL signal components has been investigated by carrying out an appropriate step annealing experiment. After each annealing at increasing temperature steps, the measurements performed include individually (a) ESR (b) OSL and subsequently residual TL and (c) solely TL measurements, similar to the procedure of T_m - T_{stop}. The primary aim of the present study includes an attempt to correlate any among the ESR centres, TL traps and OSL components in BeO if possible.

OSL dating of irrigation features: Further untapped potential?

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For many centuries groundwater has been extracted from upslope aquifers in arid regions using a form of hydraulic technology referred to as a 'shaft and gallery' system. This technology is thought to have been introduced in the early 1st millennium BC in Persia, and to have spread by diffusion both eastwards and westwards, as far as East Asia and South America, and variously referred to, for example, as a falaj, foggara, karez and qanat according to region. A distinctive feature of these features is the series of ventilation shafts that trace the route of the subterranean irrigation channel. A mound of sediment at the ground surface surrounding each ventilation shaft contains a sequence of upcast deposited during the construction and subsequent maintenance of the irrigation system. Where formed of sediment, the upcast is potentially suitable for the application of OSL techniques to obtain age estimates for the deposition and burial of the sediment. Two preliminary studies in Spain and Iran [1] have indicated the feasibility of obtaining a chronostratigraphy for shaft mounds. More detailed studies have been completed with systems in Spain, Morocco and Azerbaijan combining luminescence, sedimentological and micromorphological analysis of the upcast mounds. This paper examines the technical issues arising from an examination of the mounds studied and assesses the extent to which a complete record of deposition since initial construction is likely to survive in upcast mound deposits of this type, with a particular interest in extending the approach to other anthropogenically formed sediment structures.

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The application of full spectrum analysis to NaI(Tl) gamma spectrometry for the determination of burial dose rates

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Murray *et al.* [1] highlighted the variability in the measurement of dose rate between luminescence dating laboratories in a recent inter-comparison study. Part of this variability indicates the difficulties in homogenising and dissolving samples so that the <500 mg used in e.g. ICP-MS and NAA is representative. High resolution gamma spectrometry offers an obvious alternative to achieve a more representative and thus more accurate dose rate, because it can measure samples 100-1000 times larger. However, the high cost of the instrumentation has hindered its wide application in luminescence dating laboratories. A recent study [2] showed that a NaI(Tl) scintillator-based gamma spectrometer is also able to accurately determine burial dose rates in the natural geological samples, at a considerably lower cost. Based on a 3"×3" NaI(Tl) scintillation crystal, they reported minimum detection limits (MDL) for ⁴⁰K, ²³⁸U, and ²³²Th activity concentrations of 25, 4.8, and 2.5 Bq/kg, respectively; these data were obtained using a 250-300 g sample and an improved 3-window spectrum analysis approach. Even though these MDLs (especially for ⁴⁰K) lie about or below the lower limits found in most natural sediments, lower MDLs, especially for ²³⁸U, and ²³²Th would be desirable to achieve lower uncertainties in the derived burial dose rates.

In this study, we investigate the potential of a different approach - full spectrum analysis (FSA) [3] to reduce the MDLs. A weighted least-square regression is used in this FSA to fit three calibration standard spectra (⁴⁰K, and ²³⁸U and ²³²Th series in equilibrium) to the unknown spectrum (after subtraction of an appropriate background). Thus the FSA approach uses considerably more statistical information from each spectrum, and the additional degrees of freedom provide a direct estimate of uncertainties from the fitting process. On the other hand, it is considerably more demanding in terms of energy stability across the entire spectrum. Using our implementation of FSA, MDLs are reduced to 12 Bq/kg, 0.7 Bq/kg, and 0.6 Bq/kg for ⁴⁰K, ²³⁸U, and ²³²Th, respectively, 50-15% of those obtained with the 3-window approach. These values also compare favourably with the values from high-resolution HPGe gamma spectrometry [4]. With this new approach, 19 natural samples have been measured and analysed, and all activity concentrations lie within ±7% of the high resolution spectrometry values; the average ratio of dose rates measured on our NaI(Tl) scintillation spectrometer to those from HPGe spectrometry is 1.033±0.009 (n=19).

We conclude that our simple scintillation spectrometry system employing FSA is a useful alternative laboratory method for accurate and precise determination of burial dose rates at a significantly lower cost than high resolution spectrometry. This, combined with the large (and so more representative) sample size makes it a strong competitor to other analytical methods used in OSL dating.

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Luminescence signals of deep sea sediments in the Bengal Fan: implications for the source to sink processes over the last 6 Ma

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Quartz luminescence sensitivity has been used to study the source to sink processes in deserts, loess--paleosol sequences, fluvial and coastal sediments. However, few analyses of marine sediments have been done especially in the deep ocean. As main component of terrestrial sediments, quartz is a potential carrier to record terrigenous input change in the submarine fan. Here we report the luminescence characteristics of deep sea sediments extracted from a 330-m sequence recovered at the site U1444A during the IODP 353 Expedition in the western Bengal Fan. The quartz OSL and 110°C TL luminescence sensitivity clearly differentiates the four units (covering about 6 Ma since the late Miocene) that were identified by shipboard sedimentological investigation on the basis of the lithological properties. There is a distinct increase of quartz luminescence sensitivity in Unit 2 during the time interval of ~3.5-0.5 Ma. Detailed analysis of other luminescence properties including the proportions of fast, medium and slow components in quartz and the ratio of the k-feldspar and quartz (inferred from IRSL/[post-IR] OSL) also points to a change in Unit 2 relative to the other three units. We interpret such variabilities through the sequence as reflecting a change in the provenance over the last 6 Ma in the western Bengal Fan. We attribute the sediments with enhanced luminescence sensitivity, low proportion of slow component and increased k-feldspar/quartz in Unit 2 to the contribution from the sources associated with Indian rivers. We infer that the sediments in Units 1,3,4 with luminescence features in contrast to those in Unit 2 are mainly derived from the Himalayas weathering products. Our results are consistent with previous conclusion based on the heavy mineralogy data but disagree with the view of consistent source over the last 6 Ma. However, we are unable to distinguish the specific sources in IODP site U1444A with the present data, further investigation is needed to analyse the luminescence characteristics of sediments from potential source areas to verify our conclusions.

Optical dating of paleo-shorelines of Dawa Co, central Tibetan Plateau

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The Qinghai-Tibetan Plateau has a significant influence on atmospheric circulation and has long been a major force controlling the Asian monsoon systems. The plateau has an abundance of large inland lakes with a total area of 40,000 km², providing ideal records for paleo-environment studies. Many large lakes in closed basins of the central plateau are surrounded by high-stand paleo-shoreline systems. Based on the elevation of the highest paleo-shoreline, it was proposed that an extensive ancient lake system might have existed in the central Tibet (e.g. [1, 2]). Reliable chronology and geomorphic investigation for those paleo-shorelines are crucial for understanding lake/catchment evolution, correlating the paleo-lake levels, and regional hydrological change.

Dawa Co lies close (~40 km) to the Zhari Namco in the central plateau. Presently Zhari Namco is the 3rd largest lake in Tibet. It has been reported that its lake level has dropped by ~128 m since 8.2 ka [3]. During the high water level period, Dawa Co was suggested to have been connected to the Zhari Namco and formed a large paleo-lake of ~4000 km², which means that these two lakes should share the same highest paleo-shoreline with the same elevation and formation age. Such a geomorphic-chronologic assembly should be a typical feature for lakes in central Tibet that were past-connected but are presently-split. This general recognition can provide new insights for confirming the reliability of paleo-shorelines as the indicator of past lake levels.

In this study, optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) technique was applied to date a series of high-stand paleo-shorelines of Dawa Co. Field investigation suggested that the highest paleo-shoreline of Dawa Co (S1) has the same elevation as that of Zhari Namco (~4744 m asl). The dating results indicate that the highest shoreline has an age consistent with that of Zhari Namco (~8.2 ka), confirming that these two lakes were once linked with each other. The lake level of Dawa Co has dropped about 116 m since the early Holocene, suggesting a long-term aridity in this region. The ages for other paleo-shorelines suggest that Dawa Co was separated from Zhari Namco since the middle Holocene.

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Multi-methods luminescence dating of Batajnica loess section (Serbia)

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The loess-paleosol sequences in the Middle and Lower Danube Basin are amongst the thickest and most complete available in Europe. At the site of Batajnica in the southern Carpathian (Middle Danube) Basin, Northern Serbia, previous stratigraphy, geochemistry and magnetic susceptibility investigations identified 6 loess-paleosol alternations, the lowermost being correlated to MIS 15. Thermoluminescence ages have been reported [1] but in depth state of the art absolute dating is lacking.

In order to establish a luminescence chronology for this site, 23 samples have been collected at high resolution from the uppermost loess layer and Holocene soil, as well as from the boundaries of the three uppermost paleosols. The Single Aliquot Regenerative (SAR) protocol has been applied to 4-11 μm and 63-90 μm quartz grains. Feldspar infrared stimulated luminescence (IRSL) emitted by 4-11 μm polymineral grain was measured using the post IR-IRSL₂₉₀ technique. Quartz yielded reliable OSL ages for the samples with equivalent doses up to 220 Gy. Overall, the preliminary luminescence dating results obtained for Batajnica section further confirm the grain-size dependent discrepancy previously reported for ages as well as equivalent doses for loess samples of different origins [2]. The quartz and polymineral fine grains ages were found in agreement for equivalent doses up to 160 Gy. Ages of 39 ± 3 ka (116 Gy, 63-90 μm quartz) and 54 ± 6 ka (220 Gy, pfg) were obtained for the loess sample collected just above a potential tephra layer in the uppermost loess unit (L1), that very likely correlates with the Campanian Ignimbrite/Y5-ash layer (⁴⁰Ar/³⁹Ar dated elsewhere to 39.3 ± 0.1 ka), with a widespread occurrence in the Danube Basin [3]. At this site, for equivalent doses beyond 220 Gy the post-IR IRSL₂₉₀ protocol overestimates systematically the expected depositional moment.

Violet stimulated luminescence (VSL) along with thermally transferred optically stimulated luminescence (TT-OSL) techniques are explored in order to overcome the constraints imposed by the saturation of the fast component of the OSL signal in quartz and extend the upper age limits of the luminescence method.

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Testing the use of total beta counting for high-precision dose rate estimation

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Luminescence and ESR dating methods require an estimate of the environmental dose rate to which the sample was exposed during the burial period. Typically, beta and gamma dose rates are calculated from known sample concentrations of K, and U and Th and daughters, measured using methods such as Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass-Spectrometry (ICP-MS), HpGe gamma spectrometry, or Neutron Activation Analysis (NAA). Recently, in an inter-calibration study involving 20 laboratories [1] and using a variety of measurement techniques, the relative standard deviation of the total dose rate was found to be 12 %. This variability in dose-rate estimates was a major contributor to total variance in the age estimates, and it was concluded that there is clearly a need to increase the quality of dose-rate measurements. Unfortunately, analyses such as ICP-MS and NAA are almost always carried out by external laboratories; this makes quality control difficult (even allowing for the relatively low cost per analysis). In general, it seems preferable for dose rate measurements to be performed in-house; this allows continuous refinement of the methods used, and ongoing assessment of their accuracy and reproducibility.

To be competitive, in-house measurements require both inexpensive instrumentation and high-quality measurement procedures. Appropriate equipment is already available and includes total alpha and beta counters, and NaI gamma spectrometers. Using a new measurement and analytical procedure [2], low-level beta counters are proving a good choice of dose-rate instrumentation. They have the potential to provide precise (i.e. reproducible) measurements of the total beta activity. To convert the measured beta count rate into an accurate estimate of dose rate, two variables must be accounted for: the self-attenuation of the sample, and the source dependence in the count rate. The new measurement procedure was designed to achieve this, with the key features being:

1. A simple empirical correction for the self-absorption of the sample
2. The use of prior information on the relative contribution of the various radionuclide sources (K, U, Th)

Here we investigate the dependence of accuracy of the total dose rate on the accuracy of the prior information on K, U and Th, and show that, in routine use, this procedure leads to accurate total beta and gamma dose rates with a random uncertainties of usually <3 %; this is as good as, or better than, most alternative methods. Since the prior information on the relative radionuclide activity concentrations need not be well known, it can readily be obtained from other inexpensive instrumentation (e.g. low resolution NaI(Tl) spectrometry, [3]) permitting in-house dose rate measurements of the highest quality.

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Optical dating of young fluvial sediments from the Eastern Zhou' Citadel Wall in Puyang, central China

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It is a challenge to accurately estimate the deposition age of dim and poorly-bleached young fluvial samples in optical dating. To address the problems related to partial bleaching a number of statistical minimum age models have been developed for data analysis; all are intended to determine the dose recorded by a postulated population of well-bleached grains contained within a population of incompletely bleached grains. Single grain analysis is generally much more time consuming than multi-grain analysis (Rhodes, 2007; Medialdea, et al., 2014) and it is therefore worthwhile testing whether single grain results are in fact superior to multi-grain results. A new time-saving protocols -Simplified small aliquot SGC procedures (Hu and Li, 2018) has been proposed, but it is necessary to check its potential for dating different kinds of young water-lain sediments.

The aim of this study is to test the ability of various quartz optical dating protocols and statistical models to obtain accurate burial ages for poorly-bleached historical fluvial sediments. Three samples were collected from a fluvial sequence deposited on the top of a Citadel Wall of the Eastern Zhou Dynasty (770-256 B.C.) in Puyang city, central China. Small charcoal fragments from two of these samples were dated using AMS radiocarbon dating. Simplified small aliquot SGC, the small aliquot SAR and the single-grain SAR protocols are used, and the different statistical models are compared. The results of the various models are discussed in terms of the accuracy of the resulting age and show that simplified small aliquot SGC can save measurement time and has potential for accurately dating young fluvial sediment.

Keyword: young fluvial sediment, quartz optical dating, simplified small aliquot SGC

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Using post IR-IRSL dating of feldspar to date paleo-lacustrine sediment in yardangs, in Qaidam Basin, NE Qinghai-Tibetan Plateau

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The yardangs in arid region are important records for paleoclimatic changes and aeolian geomorphology changes. However, their formation ages are rarely studied due to the limitation of dating methods. The post-IRSL IRSL (pIRIR) dating of feldspar, with a wider dating range than quartz, is a key method in dating mid- and late Quaternary sedimentations. This method has been applied to various sediments all over the world. In this paper, pIRIR dating of feldspar were tested to find a suitable dating method for the paleo-lacustrine sediment, which have been carved into Yardangs, in Qarhan Salt Lakes Region, Qaidam Basin, NE Qinghai-Tibetan Plateau. Two main method of feldspar luminescence dating (the two-step pIRIR dating [1] which might be affected by anomalous fading, and the Multi-elevated-temperature (MET) pIRIR dating [2] which might offer non-fading ages with a D_e plateau between different stimulating temperatures) were applied. The fine-grain size polymineral and coarse-grain size K-feldspars were extracted from paleo-lacustrine sediment, and five samples were studied. The pIR₅₀IR₂₅₀ (preheat at 280 °C for 60s; stimulated at 50°C for 500 s, and then stimulated at 250°C for 500s) and MET-pIRIR (preheat at 320°C for 60 s, and stimulated at 50, 100, 150, 200, 250 and 290°C for 100s, respectively) dating results show that: (1) there is an obvious D_e plateau for MET-pIRIR dating between the stimulation temperature of 250 and 290 °C, revealing that the sediments were well bleached before buried, and the results are non-fading and reliable; (2) the pIR₅₀IR₂₅₀ ages are underestimated compared with MET-pIRIR₂₅₀ dating for all our samples, indicating that there is still anomalous fading in pIR₅₀IR₂₅₀ signals, so fading correction (measured average g-value is 2.1%/decade) is needed; (3) the corrected pIR₅₀IR₂₅₀ ages are accordant to MET-pIRIR₂₅₀ ages for both fine-grain size polymineral and coarse-grain size K-feldspars, suggesting both method are reliable for paleo-lacustrine sediments in this region; (4) the dating results of ~200-330 Ka might indicate existence of mega lakes during interglacial periods of MIS9 and MIS7 in the Qaidam Basin, which is accordant with the paleoclimatic background; (5) The absent of paleo-lacustrine sediments during glacier period might demonstrate a erosional environment, and formation of yardangs should mainly since MIS6, especially MIS4.

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Holocene landscape dynamics of the Ghaggar-Hakra fluvial system, India: implications for the demise of the Indus Civilisation

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A range of palaeoclimatic and palaeoenvironmental evidence suggests the Asian sub-continent experienced phases of arid-humid alterations on centennial and millennial scales during the Holocene, which were set against a backdrop of insolation-driven weakening of the Asian Monsoon system. These oscillations would have affected fluvial regimes on the plains of northwest India, which were occupied by the Bronze Age Indus Civilisation during the mid-Holocene. It has been suggested that a decline in regional river systems contributed to the decline of the Indus at ~4 ka [e.g. 1, 2], although in a recent study Orengo and Petrie [3] identify a complex network of buried channels on the Sutlej/Yamuna interfluves, and Durcan et al. [4] have highlighted complexity in the response of regional geomorphic systems to climatic/environmental change. Further work is therefore required to understand the spatial and temporal dynamics of regional hydrological systems in order to assess the importance of changing climate and/or environment in the decline of the Indus Civilisation

This paper presents optically stimulated luminescence dates from palaeochannel sediments and associated dune deposits on the Ghaggar-Hakra floodplain in northwest India, with particular focus on the area around the Indus site of Rakhigarhi. Rakhigarhi is the largest and potentially most important site in northwest India [5], although its relationship to local and regional fluvial systems is unclear. Reconstructing palaeoenvironmental variability will allow a comparison between the documented archaeological record of the Indus Civilisation and an absolute chronology of regional landscape dynamism. This comparison will also allow an insight into whether the mid-Holocene collapse and/or transformation of the Indus Civilisation can be correlated with geomorphological and/or climatic variability.

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Electron Spin Resonance (ESR) dating of quartz and tooth enamel from Huéscar-1 site (Guadix-Baza basin, Spain)

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Located in the North-eastern part of the Guadix-Baza basin (Southern Spain), the palaeontological site of Huéscar-1 has delivered a rich faunal assemblage made of >1200 fossil remains. A total of >30 taxa of large mammals, small mammals and birds have been identified [1], converting Huéscar-1 as a key palaeontological locality of major (local and regional) significance for both palaeoenvironmental and palaeoecological reconstructions.

In first instance, biochronological inference based on the study of the large and small mammal taxa suggested a late Early Pleistocene age estimate for the faunal assemblage [2]. Moreover, the magnetostratigraphic study of a sedimentary sequence located nearby (Puerto Lobo) provided an additional indirect evidence supporting this chronology [3]. However, a recent Luminescence dating study of the sediment enclosing the palaeontological levels yielded a significantly younger age of ~450 ka [4]. These unexpected results shed a new light on the fossil assemblage and suggested potentially more complex bone accumulation histories than initially assumed at this site.

In order to obtain an additional and independent age control for Huéscar-1, and to understand better the origin of such a major discrepancy between the Luminescence chronology and the existing magneto- biostratigraphic framework, we performed an Electron Spin Resonance dating study of several quartz samples and a fossil tooth. These materials were analysed following the most advanced analytical procedures currently available in the field. First, quartz samples were dated in accordance with the Multiple Centre approach and both the Al and Ti centres were measured. Second, combined US-ESR dating was performed on 3 different fragments collected from a given fossil tooth. The combination of the two ESR dating applications will provide not only a direct age estimate for the fossils at Huescar-1, but also a burial age estimate for the quartz grains, which will be directly comparable with the Luminescence results obtained from the same layers.

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Reconstruction of geomorphic evolution history along the lower reaches of the Fen River since the late Pleistocene constrained by luminescence dating

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As one of the longest and most important river in China, Yellow River has great impact on the formation of landscapes in northern China. Many studies had been carried on the evolution history of Yellow River. The middle reaches of Yellow River flow through the east of Chinese Loess Plateau. As the second longest tributary of the Yellow River, Fen River joins the middle reaches of Yellow River at Hejin. Linfen-Houma basin is located around the lower reaches of Fen River. Lack of studies on the evolution of the Fen River with accurate chronology limited our further understanding about the Fen River and its relationships with the Yellow River. Field investigation revealed four terraces formed by Fen River and its two tributaries (Fu River and Hui River) in the basin since the late period of Middle Pleistocene. In this study, to reconstruct the history of terrace formation and geomorphic evolution of Linfen-Houma basin, fifty-four samples were collected and measured using quartz blue-light optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating method.

The OSL ages vary from 1.5 ± 0.3 ka to 132.8 ± 10.2 ka. These dates combined with geomorphic analysis allow the reconstruction of geomorphic evolution history since the late period of Middle Pleistocene in the Linfen-Houma basin. The region experienced several “aggradation-incision” cycles. The fast incision began at ~ 78 ka, leading to the disappearance of the Linfen-Houma paleolakes. The fluvial activities turned into aggradation at ~ 55 ka, reaching a thickness up to ~ 20 meters. This was followed by incision again at ~ 15 ka. Then, there were two small scale “aggradation-incision” cycles during the Holocene.

Beta dose heterogeneity in sediment samples measured using a Timepix pixelated detector: implications for single-grain OSL dating

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Single-grain (SG) optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating has been used increasingly in Quaternary and archaeological studies to determine the depositional age of sediments. To appropriately interpret the SG equivalent dose (D_e) distribution of a given sample and ultimately derive a reliable burial dose using a suitable statistical model, understanding the source of the scatter in D_e values is essential. Beta dose rate heterogeneity is one of the major potential sources of D_e overdispersion, but beta dosimetry of sediment samples at high spatial resolution has rarely been measured at the SG scale. Studies have typically used bulk-sample measurement techniques (such as ICP-MS and beta counting) to estimate the sample-average beta dose rates. These techniques yield dose rates applicable to a large sample volume and conceal information about beta dosimetry at the SG level.

Recently, Romanyukha et al. [1] proposed a novel technique employing pixel detectors to derive spatially resolved beta dose rates for intact samples at sub-millimetre resolution using a Timepix hybrid pixelated detector. This semiconductor detector consists of an array of 256×256 pixels, each $55 \times 55 \mu\text{m}$ in size. Individual pixels can record the tracks and energies produced by particles impinging on the detector, such as alpha particles and electrons, and the particle types can be recognised from the shapes of the track clusters. Romanyukha et al. developed a measurement procedure applicable to resin-impregnated sediment samples, and tested it on an artificial micro-stratified sample. They identified the beta-particle contribution to the dose rate with sub-millimetre spatial resolution, and proposed that this technique held promise as a means of deriving spatially resolved beta dose rates at the SG scale for real and intact sediment samples.

In this study, we test the application of Timepix to five archaeological or geological sediment samples collected at two cave sites (one in Indonesia and the other in Russia) and a lunette in Australia. The samples have significant differences in inherent radioactivity and contrasting sedimentary contexts. Of key interest is the beta dose rate inhomogeneity at the SG scale within each of these samples, which were collected intact and then resin-impregnated, and the extent to which this contributes to the measured SG D_e distributions. From each sample, we prepared a sub-sample with an approximate volume of $10 \times 60 \times 6 \text{ mm}^3$ (cave sediments) or $10 \times 10 \times 6 \text{ mm}^3$ (lunette sediments) for Timepix analysis, and extracted quartz or K-feldspar grains from the sediments immediately surrounding the Timepix sample for SG (or small aliquot, SA) D_e measurement. The beta dose rate distribution of each sample was obtained by converting the beta particle count rates measured using the Timepix into dose rates using a calibration curve derived using an international standard [1]. These dose rate distributions were compared with the corresponding SG (or SA) D_e distributions, to assess the relative contribution of beta dose rate inhomogeneity to the observed spread in D_e values, and the relation of both to the micromorphology of the sediment samples. In this talk, we will present the results of our experiment and discuss the implications for SG OSL dating.

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Migration into the Asia aridity during the interglacial time in mid-Pleistocene:

evidence from the Dayao Paleolithic site

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The time for human to occupy the vast drylands in north China and the way to adapt to the wild environmental changes due to glacial-interglacial cycles are still issues in debate. Here we report a Paleolithic site, i.e. Dayao site, in Inner Mongolia, north China, located in the eastern part of Hetao which acts as a corridor to the northwest drylands. During the excavations in 1980s and 2013, >5000 piece of artifacts were discovered and are mostly proved unused as tools. Hence, the site was regarded as a workshop to produce the take-away artifacts during migration. However, up to date, the age of the site remains controversy, and environmental interpretation of the site is also ambiguous.

In this study, magnetostratigraphy and Optical Stimulation Luminance (OSL) dating methods were firstly used for age frame construction, and then the paleoclimatic changes were quantitatively reconstructed by pollen analysis and correlate with the global climatic records for further age constrains. Our results show that the high-stability characteristic remnant magnetizations component can be isolated after removing secondary magnetic component by thermal demagnetization, and only one normal magnetozone was defined by 101 oriented samples which is definitely interpreted as the Brunhes normal chron. 9 OSL samples from the site suggest that the top age is <18 ka BP, and the paleosol layers where generated many artifacts are correlated to MIS 5 and 7, respectively. By correlation our paleoclimatic data with the marine $\delta^{18}O$ records, which represents the global climatic changes, we suggest that two sandy gravel layers containing a lot of artifacts in the lower part of the sequence at least formed during MIS 9 and 11. Thereafter, our results indicate the earliest human occupation by human before 400 ka BP within a warm and humid warm interglacial period, and the subsequent occupation also mainly occurred in interglacial periods, with annual precipitation and annual temperature of 100-350mm and 0.5-4.5°C higher than today. According to the previous studies, the northward and southward displacements of northern front of the summer monsoon, comparing with the present time, during the past four interglacial and glacial cycles could be more than ~200 and ~500 km in maximum. The advance and retreatment of the summer monsoon belt have also been proved by the alternative occurrence of coarse eolian sand layers and silty clay layers of lacustrine origin presented in the borehole sediments in same region. Therefore, we conclude that the northern penetration of the summer monsoon front into the dryland in north China may provide the time window for human's migrating northwestward into the vast dryland. When summer monsoon rainbelt retreating southward during cold glacial periods, the aridification in Hetao area strengthened and led to the close of this corridor for human migration.

Direct ESR dating of human fossils

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When dating valuable human fossils, any damage has to be kept to an absolute minimum. Over the years, we have developed virtually non-destructive protocols for ESR and U-series analyses. This has given us access to a number of important human fossils, including those from Florisbad, Rising Star (Homo Naledi), Irhoud and Misliya sites. This presentation gives an overview how ESR dating has changed some of the perceptions of modern human evolution.

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A personal, 35 year long journey in ESR dating

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This presentation gives some insights of the progress made over 35 years in ESR dating of tooth enamel. When I started, samples were irradiated with four additive dose steps of 5, 10, 15 and 20 krad and the linear extrapolation yielded the dose value. An assumed dose rate of 100 mrad/a yielded the age of the sample. Since then I learned that one actually has to measure the dose rate. I also learned that the dose response can be described by a single saturating function, or perhaps two, and that errors can be appropriately calculated. Rather than having a single anisotropic CO_2^- radical, tooth enamel consists of two anisotropic CO_2^- radicals and two isotropic CO_2^- radicals, one stable, one unstable. Also, the dose response shows spatial differences in the production of these different radicals in response to beta and gamma rays. Then there is the problem of uranium uptake over time. We solved this by combining ESR and U-series analyses. We can even measure appropriate beta attenuation factors from sequential laser ablation U-series analyses. Even better, all analyses can be carried out on small enamel fragments, which can be glued back into their original position with little to no visible damage. Still, when using the most sophisticated dose rate calculations, they're often close to $1000 \mu\text{Gy a}^{-1}$. Using the lower dose range with linear fitting may compensate for the creation of unstable isotropic CO_2^- radicals. So, perhaps we were not that far off the mark some 35 years ago, or were we?

Comparison of single-aliquot and single-grain MET-pIRIR D_e results for potassium feldspar samples from the Nihewan Basin, north China

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The MET-pIRIR procedure [1, 2] has been used in dating the potassium feldspar ages either on multi-grained single aliquots or on individual grains [3], because it can successfully isolate non-fading IRSL signals.

In this study, we found that the single-grain MET-pIRIR D_e results are systematically lower than their corresponded single-aliquot MET-pIRIR D_e results for samples from the Nihewan Basin, north China. Single-grain D_e value distribution suggests that these samples are well bleached. We found that the disagreement between the single-aliquot and single-grain D_e results can be eliminated if the single grain D_e values are obtained from only brighter grains. The D_e values for dimmer grains were underestimated. The reasons for the underestimation of D_e values for dimmer grains will be discussed.

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OSL dating of the landslide-dammed event in the upper reaches of the Minjiang River, eastern Tibetan Plateau

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The chronology of landslides plays an important role in understanding their causes, frequency and hazards. Although the rapid development of Quaternary dating techniques makes multiple methods date landslides, landslide chronologies are still relatively scarce and limited due to the lack of datable materials associated with landslides. This is especially true in the eastern margin of the Tibetan Plateau, where landslides occur frequently and develop into catastrophic mass movements. For example, the 2008 Wenchuan earthquake triggered more than 30,000 landslides. In order to understand the mechanism further, it is necessary to establish the chronology of paleolandslides in the region. In this study, we tested the applicability of optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating techniques on a landslide located within the Minjiang River valley. The river flows along the Minjiang fault situated within the plateau margin close to the Sichuan Basin. Many lacustrine sediment exposures or sections on the banks of the river can be seen. It is obvious that the lakes were formed due to river blockage by landslides in the river bank cliffs. In the field, the largest landslide along the river was identified at the Diexi Town. Three exposed lacustrine sediment sections associated with the landslide-dammed lake were sampled for OSL measurements and particle size analyses.

The luminescence properties of all samples are very similar, OSL signals are dominated by fast component, and the 'Standardised growth curve' can be constructed for all the samples. Two samples close to the dam yield an age of ~12 ka; two samples farthest away from the dam dated to ~23 ka, they may represent the time of the landslide-dammed event. The other twelve samples from the ~20-m section between the two sampling locations mentioned above yield an age of ~20 ka. The grain-size distribution patterns of the twelve samples show that ten samples are mainly composed of sands, and two samples silty, suggesting that the depositional environment is relatively stable from bottom to top. The ages tend to be younger from the upper stream to the dam, implying that the dam gradually burst, and the sediments from the source were first deposited at the upper reaches, when the height of the dam became lower because of bursting, the deposition moved to the lower reaches. It also implies that the chronology of the similar landslides in the region can be constructed using luminescence dating techniques.

Paleo-environments and depositional ages of Quaternary sediments in Gyeongju, Korea

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An earthquake of a magnitude of 5.8 occurred in Gyeongju, Korea on September 12, 2016. It was the strongest earthquake ever to be observed in the Korean Peninsula. As a part of the active faulting survey, we have focused on the Quaternary stratigraphy and absolute age dating of Quaternary sediments. Establishing the Quaternary stratigraphy and reconstruction of Quaternary sedimentary processes over sub-basin of the Hyeongsan River in Gyeongju provide important information about regional distribution of Yangsan fault system and and potential of active faulting.

From the field survey and drilling, the sedimentary cores from 22 sites along the basin were acquired. In this study, their paleo-environments and depositional ages are interpreted by high precision measurements of OSL, 14C, and sediment elevation. The sedimentary sequence is normally divided into the lower debris flow deposits containing pebbly mud, and the upper fluvial deposits containing sand and mud deposits. The OSL ages of Quaternary sequences range from several hundreds to over the last 200 ka. The 14C age of the sediments give an age of ~54 Cal ky BP. However, 14C ages older than 40 ka may be unreliable, and have to be considered as a minimum age. OSL are partly inconsistent with the stratigraphic order, which indicates the effect of incomplete bleaching of the quartz grains. Nevertheless, these might constrain the minimum age of Quaternary sedimentary processes. A comparison and correlation between the stratigraphy and age dates revealed that fault-controlled incised-valley system could have occurred prior to debris flow deposition (>200 ka). After 10 ka, debris flowing system might be changed to fluvial system.

Luminescence dating of lacustrine sediments from Cuo E on the central Tibetan Plateau

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Quartz has generally been considered as the preferred dosimeter in optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating, and extensively applied in dating Holocene sediments. However, quartz OSL dating could suffer from problems on the Tibetan Plateau, because of (1) low natural OSL signals, (2) chemically irremovable feldspar contamination of quartz, and even (3) anomalous fading phenomenon [1]. Alternatively, k-feldspar is potential to provide more reliable chronologies of sediments in this area by the post-IR IRSL (pIRIR) measurement protocol.

In this study, eight sediment samples were collected from a lacustrine outcrop (CE1) in the southern shore of Cuo E (Cuo is lake in Tibetan language). Both coarse grained (90-200 μm) quartz and k-feldspar fractions were extracted from these samples. The tests on the quartz samples showed too dim OSL signals from most measured aliquots. In addition, the fading rates of the relatively bright quartz aliquots were determined, suggesting g-values of >1 %/decade and even up to 5 %/decade; this seems to indicate obvious anomalous fading and that the resulted aged is likely to be underestimated. For k-feldspar fraction of these eight samples, in contrast, a set of tests on luminescence characteristics (i.e., dose recovery and residue tests, recuperation and fading rates) were performed and demonstrate that the pIRIR protocol measured at 150°C (pIRIR₁₅₀) for our samples are reliable. The difference between a shell radiocarbon date (12.8 cal ka BP) and a k-feldspar pIRIR₁₅₀ age (7.9 ± 0.5 ka) from one sedimentary layer is probably attributed to the radiocarbon reservoir effects of ~ 4 ka during the early Holocene in the lake. Based on the stratigraphy and k-feldspar chronology of section CE1, the lake-level history could be inferred that the lake-level started to rise at 10 ka, and a high lake-level persisted during the 10-7 ka, which was followed by a lake-level drop. The lake-level variations in the current study could be related to the regional precipitation which has largely regulated by Indian summer monsoon.

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The application of SGC method employed on single grain Quartz

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Standardised Growth Curve (SGC), first proposed by Roberts and Duller [1] and further improved by Li et al. [2], has been applied in both quartz and feldspar dating. One of the main advantages of SGC is that it can considerably reduce instrument time, since the equivalent dose (D_e) can be determined based merely on measurements of the natural signal (or plus an additional regenerative dose). Recently, it was reported that the growth curve of quartz may differ significantly from grain to grain [3], which prevents the establishment of an universal SGC for single-grain quartz. In this study, we tested the variability of growth curves of single-grain quartz OSL from several sites in China, Europe and Africa. We observed a large variation in the growth curves for individual grains. Following the method of Li et al. [3], it is possible to divide the grains into several groups, and each group have similar growth curves. By establishing SGC for individual groups, we demonstrated that it is potential to extend the dating range of quartz by utilising the groups that saturated in high doses. Based on measurements on natural samples and dose recovery tests using different given doses, it is shown that establishing SGCs for single-grain quartz, together with statistical analysis on the natural signals (L_n/T_n) [4], is efficient for dealing with the problem associated with “truncated” distribution in D_e estimation for old samples [5], where a large proportion of grains are ‘saturated’.

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Lake level variations of Paiku Co revealed by OSL dating of paleo-shorelines, southern Tibetan Plateau

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Lake shrinkage and expanse is a natural response to local climate and maintains key records for paleo-environment changes such as the relative humidity and the balance between precipitation/evaporation. Lake levels, providing key information on coverage area/water volume, are one of the most important factors for reconstructing lake/catchment evolution and regional hydrological change. Paleo-shorelines are remnant structures for past lake shore and hence directly indicate past lake levels. Typically, paleo-shorelines are swash aligned ridges formed primarily of sands, pebbles and cobbles due to high-energy sedimentary environment.

Shrinking lakes and their remarkable paleo-shorelines across the Qinghai-Tibetan Plateau suggest a significant environment change and a long-term aridification in a large area of the plateau during the late Quaternary. Some of these lakes have been recently investigated. However, few studies have been carried out to date these shorelines, especially for large lakes closely linked to the Himalaya glaciers.

In this study, OSL dating was applied to investigate the paleo-shorelines of Paiku Co in the southern plateau. The modern lake level is 4585 m asl and has a coverage area of ~270 km². Unlike those lakes within the interior of the plateau (e.g. Zhari Namco in the south central Tibet) [1], Paiku Co lies close (50 km) to the Shisha Pangma Mountain (8027m asl) and its inflow receives a large portion of glacier-melt-water from the Himalaya. Climate in this region is mainly controlled by the Indian Monsoon. More than 13 distinctive paleo-shorelines were observed for Paiku Co. The highest one is about +90 m above the modern lake level. More than 20 samples were collected from those shorelines and they are mainly typical sands of lake shore deposits. During the process of lake shrinkage, two large rivers joining the lake from the south and the north incised into the former lacustrine silts/clays (formed during high-lake period), were also investigated to compare with previous radiocarbon result [2]. Our preliminary results suggest the lake has endured severe shrinkage in the late Quaternary, and the rate of shrinkage appears to be accelerating with the decrease extent of glaciers. The results also indicate that both monsoon precipitation and temperature-driven meltwater dynamics controlled lake level variations for lakes fed by glaciers.

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OSL ages from heterolithic point bar deposits in the Mekong River floodplain

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Incomplete bleaching of fluvial deposits is a potential problem in luminescence dating in many fluvial systems. Especially, attention should be given when dating fine-grained (4-11 μ m) fluvial deposits because previous studies indicated that coarser fractions of sand are generally better bleached compared to finer fractions of sand and mud [1].

The Mekong River is actively migrating and has a series of abandoned, mud-dominated, inner bank levees upstream of Phnom Penh. Precise dating of the natural levee deposits will establish the lateral migration history and time scales of levee development. The degree of bleaching of fine-grained deposits was assessed by comparing (1) the quartz OSL ages and feldspar IR₅₀ and pIRIR₁₅₀ ages and (2) the quartz OSL ages of fine-grained and sand deposits for four sand samples and two mud samples from a single, heterolithic point bar. The degree of bleaching of sand deposits was also assessed by comparing ages from different grain size fractions of sand (62-90 μ m and 211-250 μ m)

The quartz OSL ages of 62-90 μ m sand fraction of point-bar deposits (0.56-0.58 ka) are younger than those of 211-250 μ m sand fraction (0.7-1.0 ka), which suggests that 62-90 μ m sand fraction is better bleached. The feldspar pIRIR₁₅₀ ages of sand are too old (3-4 ka) to assess the degree of bleaching of quartz OSL signals. In contrast, fading corrected IR₅₀ ages of the 62-90 μ m sand fraction (0.9-1.1 ka) and 211-250 μ m sand fraction (1.1-1.2 ka) are relatively close to quartz OSL ages. However, the similarity of quartz OSL and feldspar IR₅₀ ages for the 211-250 μ m sand fraction may reflect incomplete bleaching of both quartz OSL and feldspar IR₅₀ signals because the quartz OSL ages of 211-250 μ m sand fraction are considered to be incompletely bleached. This in turn suggests that the IR₅₀ signals of 62-90 μ m sand fraction is also incompletely bleached.

The fine-grained quartz from point-bar deposits yielded ages of 0.46-0.53 ka, which is slightly younger than the quartz OSL ages of 62-90 μ m sand fraction. Although the pIRIR₁₅₀ signals of fine-grained deposits were too dim to obtain reliable ages, the fading corrected IR₅₀ ages (ca. 0.66 ka) are close to the quartz OSL ages. These analyses indicate that the finer deposits are better bleached in the Mekong River floodplain. Complete bleaching of the wash and suspended load in the Mekong River most likely reflects the long transport distance, but the high suspended load may account for incomplete bleaching of coarser bedload sediments.

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Novel dating methods using Infrared photoluminescence (IRPL)

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Feldspar is commonly dated using infrared stimulated luminescence (IRSL) which relies on electron eviction from the principle trap and its subsequent recombination with a trapped hole in the crystal lattice [1]. Recently, an alternative, non-destructive measurement technique has been developed which relies on radiative intra-defect transition within the principal trap to produce light [2], as opposed to electron-hole recombination in case of OSL/IRSL. The resulting infra-red photoluminescence (IRPL) is proportional to the trapped electron population; thus, IRPL has the potential to provide direct assessment of thermal and optical stabilities, as well as the behaviour of trapped electrons during different laboratory protocols. This information is important both for evaluating the accuracy of optical dating (including thermochronometry and rock surface dating), and for designing new laboratory procedures/instruments for the measurement of equivalent dose.

Prasad et al. [2] identified a single, Stokes-shifted near-infrared (NIR) emission at ~ 1.30 eV (955 nm) using laser excitation at ~ 1.40 eV (885 nm). Subsequently, Kumar et al. [3] have shown that there exist two IRPL emissions at ~ 1.41 eV (880 nm) and ~ 1.30 eV (955 nm) by shifting the laser excitation energy to ~ 1.49 eV (830 nm). The two emissions can be discriminated in the Risø TL-OSL reader using IR laser excitation, and detection through a combination of bandpass interference filters and appropriate NIR photomultiplier tubes or an imaging camera [4]. Sellwood et al. [5] have applied the IRPL techniques to rocks, and shown that IRPL can be used to directly map optical bleaching front without extensive sample preparation involved in coring and slicing.

In conventional dating protocols a single trapped electron can be measured at most only once. However, since IRPL is non-destructive (i.e. same trapped electron can be measured repeatedly), it has extremely high sensitivity which makes it possible to integrate it into the existing SAR protocols developed for infra-red stimulated luminescence (IRSL) and post-IR IRSL (pIR-IRSL), without affecting the measurements. Such a possibility allows both simultaneous dose measurement using IRPL/IRSL/pIR-IRSL as well as monitoring of changes in the trapped electron population during different SAR protocols.

Here, we provide an overview of the performance of the two IRPL emissions (~ 1.41 eV (880 nm) and ~ 1.30 eV (955 nm)). We present new results on 1) behaviour of the principle trap under different thermal and optical conditions, and 2) sediment dating (equivalent dose, dose recovery, characteristic dose etc.) from a set of feldspar samples. We discuss these results in terms of a refined feldspar model and future potential of IRPL.

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OSL Dating Ages and Hydrological Implications of Paleoflood Deposits in the South Margin of Badain Jaran Desert

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The Badain Jaran Desert is worldly famous by coexistence of lakes and megadunes in the southeastern part of the desert. The groundwater origin of Badain Jaran desert was a hotly debated issue in the last decade. Aqueous sediments was important sedimentary archive for understanding the paleo-information of the surface water in this region. In this study, paleoflood deposits, Yaburi (YBR) section, was discovered in the south margin of Badain Jaran desert. The paleoflood deposits consist mainly of mud, silty mud, and fine sand, with a total thickness of 20.5 m. Based on the identification criteria, 4 paleoflood SWDs (Slack Water Deposits, SWDs) were identified: 14.035-15.105m (SWD1), 9.42-10.07m (SWD2), 3.55-6.39m (SWD3), 0-2.66m (SWD4) (Huang et al., 2011; Benito, et al., 2015). For optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating uses quartz, seven samples were collected from the deposits. In the laboratory, the fine quartz (4~11 μ m) of all samples were selected according to Stoke's Law using acetone and deposited on stainless steel discs. The quartz purity was checked with infrared stimulation (Li, 2002). The luminescence measurements were performed using a Daybreak-2200 automatic system equipped with blue light simulation (470 \pm 5 nm) and infrared simulation (880 \pm 80 nm) in the Key Laboratory of Quaternary Chronology and Environment Evolution, CAGS. Based on the OSL dating ages, SWDs age span were calculated by interpolation method: 168.7~164.4 ka (SWD1), 142.4~139.1 ka (SWD2), 124.6~87.5 ka (SWD3), 79.3~64.2 ka (SWD4). Compared with the ages of the elevated paleo-lake deposits, we suggest that the paleoflood events mainly occurred during the warm and humid period, when the lakes has a higher water level. Based on the location and ages of the paleoflood deposits, we propose that the rainfall water in the Beida Mountains recharge to the groundwater and lakes of Badain Jaran desert through surface flood flow during the humid periods. And, the SWDs formed where the surface water was blocked by the mega-dunes. However, the frequency of paleoflood events and its contribution to the groundwater of Badain Jaran desert need more future studies.

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TL properties and dating of various Mediterranean calcium carbonate minerals of old ages

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Calcium carbonate, with the chemical formula CaCO₃, stands among the most widespread minerals of earth's crust. The importance of dating calcium carbonate based formations for setting age limits has been well demonstrated by both the uranium series disequilibrium method as well as Electron Paramagnetic Resonance (EPR) techniques. As far as luminescence techniques are concerned, the lack of optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) signal makes thermoluminescence (TL) the only luminescence technique available for dating applications for these formations. Throughout the literature, the TL properties of various types of CaCO₃ samples have been repeatedly reported; nevertheless the yielded ages were in most cases lower than 500 ka. The present study reports TL properties of different calcium carbonate samples collected from different sampling sites all over Turkey. Preliminary OSL and thermally assisted OSL (TA-OSL) measurements verify the lack of useful signals for dosimetry purposes. For all these samples, the additive dose TL procedure has been effectively applied for the paleodose estimation, using quite large additive doses. Linearity of TL dose response was highly established. The extremely low concentrations of natural radionuclides, along with the high paleodose values, result in ages of the order of 1 Ma or even some larger. These ages stand among the oldest ages reported in the literature of luminescence dating. Additionally, the lifetime of the main dosimetric trap was calculated for each sample using deconvolution.

Luminescence chronologies of different size fractions of quartz in the Korean Peninsula

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The choice of grain size for optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating is governed by availability within the samples. An age comparison of different grain-size fractions has given rise to conflicting results over recent years. In many cases, the luminescence ages yielded by each grain-size fraction analyzed are consistent within errors limits. However, some studies have reported that the use of OSL for fine-grained quartz can lead to the underestimation of age. However, there are also cases that OSL ages of fine-grained quartz were consistently older than those of coarse-grained quartz. Many previous studies have been focused on a single section, thus it is uncertain whether the age discrepancy is a regional phenomenon or not. This study attempts to summarize the significant factor to cause the age discrepancy in each grain-size fraction. We also investigated the luminescence characteristics and the suitability of OSL dating for different quartz grain sizes from fluvial and coastal sediments in the Korean Peninsula. The accuracy of OSL dating results from different quartz grain sizes was evaluated by comparison with independent age control.

Instrumentation for infrared photoluminescence (IRPL) measurement in feldspar

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Optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) or Infra-red stimulated luminescence (IRSL) are typically measured in an anti-Stoke's emission mode; the signal decays rapidly during optical stimulation. In contrast Infra-red PhotoLuminescence (IRPL), first detected in feldspar at ~950 nm by Prasad et al. [1], is a Stoke's shifted emission stimulated by near-IR radiation. Subsequently Kumar et al [2] have shown that there exist two IRPL emissions in feldspar [2]. IRPL results from excitation-relaxation within the trap [1, 2] and does not involve hole-centre recombination. It can thus be measured over long periods without significant signal loss, by repeated excitation of trapped electrons; this is especially true for electron traps with a large distance to the nearest recombination site (i.e. non-fading traps).

Prasad et al. [1] demonstrated IRPL using the Risø station for Cryogenic Luminescence Research (COLUR) which is not convenient for routine dosimetric measurements. For later dosimetric investigations, Prasad et al. used the spectrometer attachment to the Risø TL/OSL reader; this is based on a spectrograph and an EMCCD camera. We have observed that the wavelength of the IRPL emission peak is nearly invariant across samples, and thus measurement can be optimised using broad bandpass detection. The new Risø IRPL measurement system uses a laser light source at 1.49 eV (830 nm), and two photomultiplier tubes (PMT) for detecting emissions at ~1.41 eV (880 nm) and ~1.3 eV (955 nm) or an Electron-Multiplying Charged Couple Device (EM-CCD) camera. Pulsed IRPL measurement in the PMT detection mode ensures a low background count rate by allowing the rejection of breakthrough from excitation light.

The IRPL emissions has been recently applied to high resolution mapping of trapped charge in rocks [3], correlations with geochemistry [4], and sediment dating [5] applications. We demonstrate here the potential of the IRPL attachments using result from typical natural feldspar (multiple grains and single grains) samples.

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Chronology for the Huxushan Paleolithic site in south China using multiple luminescence dating techniques

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The Huxushan archaeological site is one of Pleistocene Palaeolithic sites in Hunan Province, South China. However, most of the sites including Huxushan have not been dated due to the lack of suitable numerical dating materials. Optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) techniques were tried to date these sites using quartz grains extracting from sediments, which are intensively chemically weathered, resulting in disappearance of most of feldspar minerals within them [1]. Although the quartz grains demonstrated excellent luminescence characteristics relevant to the single-aliquot regeneration dose (SAR) method [1], the quartz SAR-OSL ages obtained are considered to be underestimated by comparing with the post-infrared infrared stimulated luminescence (pIRIR) ages on fine-grained feldspar [2]. In order to further confirm these results, in this study we try to date the Huxushan site from the same area using the OSL-SAR and TT-OSL SAR protocols on fine-grained quartz and the high-temperature pIRIR procedure on medium-grained feldspar grains. In the absence of any other independent age controls for these sites, the reliability of the luminescence ages can only be evaluated from the internal comparison of the ages obtained using different luminescence signals or minerals besides stratigraphical order. In this study, seven samples have been investigated, and the preliminary experiments show that the fine quartz grains are very sensitive to preheat temperature, as supported by dose recovery tests. The final results will be presented in the poster.

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High resolution luminescence chronologies of loess records in northern slope of Tianshan Mountains revised paleoclimatic changes in arid central Asia

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Arid central Asia (ACA) is one of the driest regions in the world and is a main source area of global atmospheric dust. Thick Loess records of paleoclimatic changes in ACA are complex and interpretations are problematic due primarily to the lack of robust chronologies. In this study, quartz OSL dating and a new developed K-feldspar pIRIR dating were employed to date 50 samples from a 45 m thick loess sequence (QS16 section) on the northern slope of the Tianshan Mountains, central ACA. The reliability of K-feldspar ages were monitored by internal checks of luminescence characteristics and further confirmed by comparing with reliable quartz OSL ages. An age depth model were established using quartz OSL and K-feldspar pIRIR ages using Bacon age depth modelling. In combination with section lithology, proxy indexes of grain size and magnetic susceptibility, CaCO₃, Color, Our results indicated that: (1) quartz OSL ages and K-feldspar pIRIR ages are reliable for loess samples in ACA up to 40 ka and 260 ka, respectively. (2) Loess begin to be deposited on the northern slope of Tianshan Mountains at least by 260 ka from ACA, loess in ACA was mainly deposited during glacial periods. Dust emission and Loess deposition in ACA are closely related to glacial-interglacial climatic cycles, Unique quick dust emission and loess deposition occurred during late MIS 6 and early MIS 4 and MIS 2 periods in ACA.(3) The continues aridity environment was prevailed in the basins and northern slope of Tianshan mountains during past three glacial-interglacial cycles, and extremely dry environmental were occurred during MIS 6 and MIS 4, and MIS 2 periods of glacial, which is much different to moist interglacial-dry glacial pattern in East Asia. (4) Depositional hiatus were frequently appeared at different elevations spanning different periods of ~50 ka to few ka in the ACA. A high resolution chronology is necessary for ACA loess records climatic change reconstructions. Interglacial dust emission decreasing and glacial deflation are possibly responsible for loess depositional hiatus in ACA.

Active folding of the Anjihai anticline in the northern Tian Shan constrained by luminescence dating

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The piedmont of northern Tian Shan is characterized by rows of fault-related folds, which propagate from the south to the north due to the thrusting of Southern Junggar Faults during the late Cenozoic. Anjihai anticline, located at the northern front of forward propagating deformation, provides a natural observatory for studying the growth of active fold in three dimensions. The late Quaternary deformation rate of Anjihai anticline has been investigated, as well as its relationship with the Halaande anticline, to the west of Anjihai anticline. The deformation of the eastern tip of Anjihai anticline is quantified by structural and geomorphologic mapping, and DEM analysis.

Samples for luminescence dating were collected from the deformed fluvial terrace and related sediments. Coarse grain quartz and potassium rich-feldspar grains are extracted. The blue light stimulated luminescence signal of quartz, and post-infrared infrared stimulated luminescence signal of potassium feldspar grains are employed to date the samples deposited in the Holocene and beyond, respectively. Due to the potential partial bleaching of luminescence signals of fluvial sediments before deposition, single grain technique is used for equivalent dose determination to identify the fully bleached grains. The evolution of Anjihai anticline is constrained by combining the deformation pattern and the OSL ages. Our preliminary data suggest that the eastern tip of Anjihai anticline has significantly deformed since the Last Interglacial.

Study on the thermal activation of ESR signal intensity in quartz E₁' center

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The E₁' center in quartz is an important paramagnetic defect, and the maximum value of its thermal activation ESR signal intensity has many new applications, but there are different views on the method for obtaining the maximum value of the E₁' center intensity. In order to further study and discuss the enhancement mechanism of the quartz E₁' center and the condition for obtaining the maximum ESR signal intensity of the quartz E₁' center, we used electron spin resonance (ESR) technique to measure the intensities of the quartz E₁' center of two moraine samples before and after the 300°C isothermal heating. The results show that the signal intensity of the E₁' center is enhanced with the increase of irradiation dose at room temperature due to the formation of the counterfeit E₁' center^[1], while the intensity of E₁' center decreases with the increase of radiation dose may due to the gamma ray irradiation cause the real E₁' center to decay. The isothermal annealing experiments of quartz E₁' center at 300°C (for 15 min and 20 min respectively) indicate that the pre-irradiation is needed for obtaining the maximum value of the E₁' center signal intensity, and the effect of artificial irradiation is not only to provide more holes^[2,3], but also to facilitate the conversion of oxygen vacancies to E₁' center.

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Variations in luminescence sensitivity of quartz from two Tajik loess sections

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Differences in quartz luminescence sensitivity have been widely observed in loess and paleosol samples. However, there is still a lack of consensus on the causes of such differences. In this study, we examine luminescence sensitivity of quartz grains from two loess sections in southern Tajikistan, Central Asia. Both pattern and amplitude in the vertical variations of quartz luminescence sensitivity of these two sections are similar, characterized by higher values in paleocomplex units and lower values in the loess units. Good correlations were found between the luminescence sensitivity and other climate proxies, such as frequency-dependent magnetic susceptibility, grain size and IRSL/[post-IR] OSL ratios, suggesting a paleoenvironmental control on the variation of luminescence sensitivity for the loess in Central Asia. Our experiments with repeated bleaching/irradiation cycles and thermal activation revealed different degrees of increment in quartz luminescence sensitivity for the samples from different lithologies. The samples with lower luminescence sensitivity are more likely to be sensitised. Thermal activation experiments also display large variability in behaviours of luminescence sensitivity for samples in different grain sizes. These results imply that the quartz samples with different luminescence characters might be from different sources. Given the diversity of the bedrocks in the Central Asian orogenic belt and their difference in resistance to weathering, the luminescence characteristics of derived quartz grains in loess sequence would be expected to vary. We suggest that the variation in quartz luminescence sensitivity in the study area is controlled by the weathering history of the parent rock types in the provenance since penultimate interglaciation.

The sensitivity characteristic of quartz ESR signals in fluvial sediments

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Experimental phenomena show that the transport-deposit processes of river will enhance the luminescence (thermoluminescence and optically stimulated luminescence) sensitivity of quartz ^[1]. However, there is no correlation study about whether quartz ESR signal sensitivity will also be enhanced during the transport-deposit processes of river.

The transport processes of river can bleach Al centre ESR signal of quartz to a stable residual value and Ti-Li centre ESR signal of quartz to zero. So, Al centre and Ti-Li centre ESR signals of quartz are often used in sediment dating. In order to study the sensitivity characteristics of Al and Ti-Li ESR signals in quartz, we collected the first terrace samples in different segments (Yichang, Wuhan and Nanjing) of Yangtze River respectively because the Ti-Li center ESR signal intensity of quartz of present sample is zero or very weak .

Grain sizes fractions (100-200 μm) of samples were extracted by wet sieving. After sieving, pure quartz was obtained through chemical separation techniques ^[2], and divided into 200 mg aliquots. At the end, these aliquots have received 100 Gy and 300 Gy additional gamma doses using the ⁶⁰Co gamma source of Peking University.

ESR measurements were carried out on a BRUKER ER041XG X-band spectrometer in a finger dewar cooled to 77 K with liquid nitrogen in the ESR laboratory of the Institute of Geology, China Earthquake Administration. The experimental parameters were microwave power 5 mW and modulation amplitude 0.16 mT. The Ti-Li center intensity was measured from the top of the peak at $g=1.979$ to the bottom at $g=1.913$ ^[2, 3]. The angular dependence of the ESR signal due to the sample heterogeneity was taken into account. Each aliquot was measured with six rotations, in which scan six times after every 60° azimuths rotation in the cavity, to obtain the average quartz Ti-Li center ESR intensity.

The results show that there have a positive correlation between the sensitivity of both quartz Al center and Ti-Li center ESR signals and the distance of transportation. That is, the sensitivity of both quartz Al center and Ti-Li center ESR signals at Nanjing (S_N) and Wuhan (S_W) and Yichang (S_Y) is $S_N > S_W > S_Y$. Thus, quartz ESR signal sensitivity will also be enhanced during the transport-deposit processes of river.

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Constraining the eruption age of Datong group of volcanoes using luminescence

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To constrain the eruption age of Datong group of volcanoes, northern China, both the luminescence and K-Ar dating methods were applied to the lava-baked sediment, unbaked sediment and the overlying lava separately at four different sites (Yujiazhai, Dongshuitou, Heishan and Huangjiawa). Here we discuss the results obtained using luminescence methods with K-Ar ages providing the independent chronological framework. The optically stimulated luminescence (OSL), thermally-transferred OSL (TT-OSL) responses of fine-grained quartz (4-11 μm) and post-infrared infrared stimulated luminescence (post-IR IRSL or pIRIR) signal of fine-grained polymineral (4-11 μm) were used to determine the equivalent dose. Measurements consisted of a simplified single-aliquot regenerative dose protocol for TT-OSL^[1,2] and a two-step Infra-red Stimulated Luminescence (IRSL) at 50 and 290 °C for the post IR-IRSL protocol (pIRIR₂₉₀)^[3].

Based on K-Ar, the eruption ages for the four sampling sites (Yujiazhai, Dongshuitou, Heishan and Huangjiawa) are older than 200 ka. The pIRIR₂₉₀ signal from all the samples was found to be in field saturation (no systematic increase in equivalent dose with depth) and laboratory saturation (apparent mean burial dose ~900 Gy). At Yujiazhai, Dongshuitou and Heishan sites, the equivalent doses of TT-OSL signal were found to be comparable with pIRIR₂₉₀ signal, despite the TT-OSL signal being well below saturation defined by the laboratory growth curve. However, at Huangjiawa site, the equivalent doses of TT-OSL are much smaller than that of pIRIR₂₉₀. Compared with the lava K-Ar ages (ranging between 0.33-1.19 Ma), both the TT-OSL and pIRIR₂₉₀ ages represent the minimum values.

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Zeroing of four MET-pIRIR signals of modern riverbed cobbles from the Manas river, Tian Shan

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Fluvial cobbles are amongst the most challenging Quaternary deposits for dating. Optically stimulated luminescence dating of buried rock surfaces has attracted much interest over the past few years (Sohbati et al., 2012, 2015; Freiesleben et al., 2015; Jenkins et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2018). However, few systematic studies exist on the resetting of the luminescence signal in modern gravels and fluvial terrace gravels in a dynamic river transport system, where processes such as abrasion and sorting may be important (e.g. Liu et al., 2018). In this study we report on an investigation of daylight bleaching in modern riverbed cobbles with different grain sizes, shapes, and settings from the Manasi River, Tian Shan, to test the reliability and applicability of fluvial cobble optical dating. Four MET-pIRIR signals are measured using a modified multi-elevated-temperature post-infrared infrared stimulated luminescence (MET-pIRIR) protocol. Residual luminescence depth profiles of four MET-pIRIR signals are established and residual doses of surface rock slices from these cobbles are estimated.

OSL dating of Quaternary sediments in the foreland basin of NW Taiwan: a new aspect of terrace morphology and sea level change

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Depositional terraces in northwestern Taiwan are distributed along the foreland basin besides the west side of the Neogene mountain ranges. These Quaternary aggradational terraces are the result of subsequent sedimentation, tectonic uplift and erosion [1]. Three categories of sediments are classified by their elevation and morphology: 1) *sedimentary highland "SH"* (> 250 m, mainly at the east side), 2) *sedimentary terraces "ST"* (250 – 50 m, in the central part) and 3) *fluvial terraces in the riverbank and coastal plain "AL"* (< 50 m, mainly along the coastal area at the west side)[2]. These sediments conformably overlie the Tertiary shallow-marine depositional strata [3], demonstrating that the sedimentary facies alter from shallow marine environment, followed by a tidal flat system and beach sediments, to an alluvial facies, and covered by aeolian deposits. Subsequent fluvial incision started after the aeolian deposition and is the driving force for the forming of the terraces. In order to understand the sedimentary processes of the terraces, luminescence dating approaches have been applied to determine the timing of the terrace sedimentation. Coarse-grained quartz and K-feldspar fractions were employed for OSL measurement. The samples from the beach sediment layers are out of the upper dating ranges for both the quartz OSL and K-feldspar post infrared (IR) IRSL signals. The lower boundary of the gravel bed on the "ST" yielded OSL ages of ca. 30ka, while the lower boundary of the gravel bed on the "AL" yielded OSL ages of ca. 18ka. Combined with the geomorphological mapping and tectonic features, the luminescence chronology was used to interpret the sedimentary processes in northwestern Taiwan since the late Pleistocene. The spatial distribution of the different depositional ages indicates the transportation of the gravels from the "ST" to the "AL". We use an uplift rate of 1mm/yr for further discussion of the surface processes [4]. Moreover, the occurrence of shallow marine sediments across the study area indicates that the foreland basin besides the west side of the Neogene mountain ranges was filled by tidal-flat and beach sediments during at least one sea-level high stand. The following regression triggered the fluvial response and the subsequent erosion of these sediment units. The eustatic sea-level low stand in the Pleistocene accelerated the incision speed. Once the gravels were eroded, the fluvial valleys are getting wider by denudation and lateral erosion. Finally, the elevated erosional base during the early Holocene triggered the latest deposition of the gravels in the coastal area. We assume that the combination of tectonic processes, eustatic sea-level changes and surface processes is responsible for the landform development in the study area. Our results are in accordance with local and regional environmental changes during the late Quaternary in the Asia-Pacific region.

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Optically stimulated luminescence dating of the terraces of the Beida River in the northern Qilian mountains and its environmental significance

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River terraces are good carriers for recording tectonic activity and climate change. To study the tectonic activities and climate changes since the Holocene in the Northern Qilian Mountains, we used the Optically Stimulated Luminescence dating to measure the ages of the Beida River terraces in this area. The river cut at a depth of about 120m. The different types of sediments of T3, T4, and T5 terraces of two sequences were measured. The study found that: (1) The ages of the terraces of T3 (eolian sediments) , T4 (the floodplain sediments) , and T5 (eolian sediments) on the right bank of the Power Station (2.5 km from the Yamaguchi) were measured at around 4.8 ka. The age of the paleochannel on the T3 terrace was slightly later (0.4ka) than the T3 terrace. (2) The ages of the bottom of the eolian sediments of the terrace sequences T3, T4, and T5 on the left bank of the Power Station are measured at (6.4 ± 0.5) ka, (4.7 ± 0.4) ka and (6.4 ± 0.6) ka. The bottom age of ancient yoke lacustrine deposits on terrace T3 was measured at (5.9 ± 0.4) ka, and the top age was measured at (5.3 ± 0.4) ka. The formation ages of T3, T4, and T5 terraces are all concentrated around 5-6 ka. It is indicated that during this period, significant climate change occurred in the Beida River, resulting in rapid river cutting and a series of river terraces.

Chronology of Daluze paleolake deposits in the North China Plain

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Daluze was once of the largest lake in the North China Plain. It has been dry in the early twentieth century. The lacustrine sediments in this area provide valuable material for the study of palaeoenvironmental changes. In this study, sediment samples collected from Yanchi section, where is close to the centre of the Daluze palaeolake, were dated with Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL) method using fine (4-11 μm) quartz. AMS (Accelerator Mass Spectrometry) ¹⁴C method was also conducted to the samples at the top of two lacustrine layers. The OSL ages of all the samples are generally in stratigraphic order, although the ages from silt layers were overestimated slightly. For samples collected from the lacustrine layers, the OSL ages with fine grain fractions are in good agreement with the ¹⁴C ages. Based on the dating results, the ages of the lacustrine sediments are in the periods of 12.3 to 5 ka and 4.5 to 1.0 ka. Floods took place at about 5 ka and since 1 ka ago. The environmental changes are affected by the global climate in this area.

Luminescence dating of Holocene lake highstand in Jinchang paleolake, NE Tibetan Plateau

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Lake shoreline beach ridges and their sediments have often been investigated as palaeoenvironmental indicators in the arid northern China. Robust chronology is crucial to utilize this archive for palaeoenvironmental reconstruction and interpretation. This study conducts the luminescence dating using both quartz and K-feldspar fractions of three samples from the highest wave-built beach ridge from Jinchang paleolake at the NE margin of the Tibetan Plateau. The applicability of the selected measurement procedures is validated by a set of internal tests on luminescence characteristics such as preheat plateau test and dose recovery test, and the reliability of the resulting three pairs of luminescence ages are also confirmed by agreement with three independent ¹⁴C ages. The beach ridge is dated to around 8-6.5 ka based on the luminescence ages. This constructed chronologies are also thought to be robust in the stratigraphic context. The results are interpreted as a distinct period of lake highstand, which has also been identified in other lakes nearby [1]. The Holocene highstand of Jinchang paleolake could be correlated to the regional moisture condition which is dominantly regulated by the Asian summer monsoon precipitation.

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Improvements of rock surface luminescence dating by thinner slices and regenerative-dose normalization

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One of the most important tasks for optically stimulated luminescence dating of exposure rock surfaces is to establish residual luminescence depth profiles. The thickness of rock slice is undoubtedly very important to obtain a good OSL depth profiles. We could cut rock into slices as thin as 0.2 mm thick now by using the diamond wire-sawing. Within the same depth in the rock core, we can get 2-3 times more slices (data points) than others [e.g., 1, 2] to reduce uncertainties of the profiles greatly. More importantly, the 0.2 mm thick rock slice would ensure that stimulated IRSL penetrates the slices completely, and has the same thickness as the coarse grains (180-250 μm), which means we don't need to calibrate the beta source for rock slices.

In the previous studies, the sensitivity-corrected natural IRSL signals (Ln/Tn) from rock slices were measured by using IRSL or elevated temperature post-IR IRSL protocol [1, 2]. However, the change in luminescence sensitivity between measurement of the natural signal and stimulation of the subsequent test doses (i.e., the k value) would affect measured Ln/Tn values. Scatter of data point in the OSL depth profiles, dispersion of the saturated test dose sensitivity-corrected OSL signals among the slices can be greatly reduced by normalising the sensitivity-corrected Ln/Tn using one of the regenerative dose OSL signals (i.e. re-normalisation; [3]). Samples with different lithology are investigated in this study, the quality of OSL depth profile looks much better when using thinner slices and regenerative-dose normalization.

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Dose response correlation between thermoluminescence and optically stimulated luminescence in un-doped magnesium oxide

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Magnesium oxide (MgO), in its un-doped form, yields average thermoluminescence (TL) sensitivity. Its potential applicability in TL dosimetry has been exploited many decades ago. Nevertheless, due to a number of reasons, which include (a) composite glow curve structure, (b) relatively low sensitivity and (c) high variability of its TL properties depending on the synthesis technique, magnesium oxide has not found wide acceptance as a practical TL detector yet. Nevertheless, the specific material, even in its un-doped form, has a high optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) sensitivity, higher than that of TL. The present work presents, for the case of un-doped, commercial MgO, a comparative, component-resolved dose response study for (a) the TL (b) the linearly modulated (LM-)OSL measured at room temperature and (c) the LM-OSL measured at 170 °C. A computerized glow curve deconvolution (CGCD) analysis was applied to all experimental OSL and TL glow curves. All TL glow curves, as well as all residual TL (R-TL) after each LM-OSL measurement were deconvolved using the exactly same trapping parameters of each peak. It was found that each peak and each LM-OSL component follow its own dose response behaviours. Based on the corresponding supra-linearity index values, a correlation between specific, individual TL peak and LM-OSL components was, in principle, possible.

Holocene loess in Illinois revealed by OSL dating: implications for stratigraphy and geoarchaeology of the Midwest United States

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Most uplands in Illinois are blanketed by late-Wisconsinan Peoria Loess, and the conventional wisdom is that little or no dust accumulation occurred during the Holocene (11.7 ka to present). In a recent effort to investigate if Illinois Holocene loess was deposited and preserved, we applied optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating to seven locations where loess is thick. These include four sites along the Mississippi River in westernmost Illinois, and three loess bluffs south of the Illinois River in central Illinois. Our results suggest that Holocene-aged loess is preserved along the Mississippi River in the state of Illinois; in contrast, no Holocene loess was found south of the Illinois River in the central portion of the state. In addition to its spatially limited distribution, Holocene loess thicknesses range only up to 1 m. Nevertheless, loess stratigraphy and OSL dating results provide the first Holocene loess reported east of the Missouri River. Our new finding also resolves the long-time archaeological puzzle that a number of artifacts of several thousand years old were buried by upland loess along the Mississippi River.

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Internal dose rates to perthitic grains

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Optical dating of potassium feldspar (K-feldspar) has become more common in recent years due to the development of post-infrared infrared stimulated luminescence protocols. This has led to the need to characterise the dose rates delivered to grains from radionuclides, especially potassium-40 (⁴⁰K), present in their crystal lattices. Pure K-feldspar (KAlSi₃O₈) contains ~14 wt.% potassium (K) within its crystal lattice; however, detrital K-feldspars derived from igneous terranes are often not pure. K-feldspar is an endmember in the alkali feldspar series, the other endmember being sodium feldspar (Na-feldspar; NaAlSi₃O₈). At magmatic temperatures, alkali feldspars form a solid solution series, resulting in the crystallisation of alkali feldspars with both K and Na in their crystal lattices (e.g., sanidine and anorthoclase). As these crystals cool (e.g., during the crystallisation of a magma reservoir), alkali feldspars form a miscibility gap between the K and sodium (Na) endmembers, resulting in the exsolution (i.e., unmixing) of two separate feldspar phases: K- and Na-feldspar (e.g., orthoclase, microcline and albite). The exsolution of separate K- and Na-feldspar phases often presents itself in the form of perthitic textures; that is, fine intergrowths of one endmember existing in a matrix of the other endmember. This may cause the K concentration—and, thus, ⁴⁰K concentration—to vary for individual sand-sized grains, such as those used in optical dating [1].

Most optical dating studies etch their grains with hydrofluoric acid in order to remove the external alpha contribution to the dose rate; however, Na-feldspars may be less resistant to chemical weathering than K-feldspars [2], resulting in the preferential removal of Na-feldspar intergrowths [3]. Thus, K content measurements made on etched grains may not be reflective of the K contents of the grains in nature. In this study, we used energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) to compare the K contents for individual etched and unetched perthitic grains to determine if there is a bias in using etched or unetched grains for determination of K contents. In addition to this, we tested the use of luminescence characteristics as proxies for K contents for individual grains, following on from Smedley *et al.* [1]. The implications for determination of internal dose rates to perthitic grains will be discussed.

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Analyzing statistical models for equivalent dose and burial age determination using a Markov Chain Monte Carlo method

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In optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating, statistical age models for equivalent dose (D_e) distributions are routinely estimated using the maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) method. In this work a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method was used to analyse statistical age models that are widely applied in OSL dating (such as the central age model, the minimum age model, etc). Firstly the method was employed to obtain the sampling distributions on parameters of interest in an age model by MCMC sampling using D_e distributions from individual sedimentary samples. Then the method was extended to derive age estimates from multiple samples with stratigraphic constraints simultaneously. This method allows the use of Bayesian methods to refine chronological sequences from multiple samples, including both fully and partially bleached OSL dates. Simulated D_e distributions are used to validate the reliability of dose (age) estimates obtained through this method. Easily-implemented open-source numeric programs are developed to perform the MCMC sampling. The results demonstrate that estimates obtained using the MCMC method can be used as an informative comparison for the MLE method. Analysis of multiple OSL dates with stratigraphic orders using the MCMC method may significantly improve both the precision and accuracy of burial ages.

TL, OSL and IRSL properties of various natural and commercial gypsum samples

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Gypsum is a soft sulfate mineral composed of calcium sulfate dihydrate, with the chemical formula $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. It is widely mined and among the plethora of its applications, in both forms of dihydrate and anhydrate, the most important is being the main constituent in many forms of plaster in art objects, such as sculptures as well as ground layers in many cases of portable oil paintings. Despite the quite wide use and application of gypsum, so far in the literature very limited studies deal with its luminescence properties in few gypsum samples only. In the framework of the present study, luminescence results are presented for six different gypsum samples of both natural and commercial origin all over the globe. All gypsum samples yield stable thermoluminescence (TL) peaks, suitable for dating, within the temperature range between 200 °C and 350 °C (heating rate 2°C/s). These TL peaks contribute to the intense signal of both optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) and infrared stimulated luminescence (IRSL). Dosimetric properties such as the shape of the TL glow curves, the stability of the corresponding TL peaks, the dose response and the minimum detectable dose limit of TL, OSL and IRSL signals are quite important in a feasibility study of gypsum as an alternative chronometer. Moreover, there are experimental hints that the chemical reaction of gypsum with water could be an extremely effective zeroing mechanism for the TL signal. The validity of this feature is being studied for all types of stimulated luminescence signals, namely TL, OSL and IRSL. Among the primary aims of this work is to study whether these aforementioned TL features are of prevalent, universal nature over all samples. For all samples, a structural and compositional characterization was performed using XRD and FTIR techniques.

Luminescence ages from quartz and feldspar (post-IR IRSL) and ^{10}Be exposure ages of Late Pleistocene terrace deposits at the deformation front of central Taiwan

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With the chief goal of better estimating long-term deformation rates and assessing seismic hazard, this study combines luminescence dating and cosmogenic radionuclide exposure dating in the challenging setting of the foothills of the Taiwan mountain belt, where conglomeratic alluvial terraces are capped by thick soil. In central Taiwan, the deformation front is marked by a blind thrust, the Changhua thrust, responsible for the growth of the Pakuashan anticline. The Choushui River, the largest river of Taiwan, cuts through the southern end of the anticline and formed six alluvial terraces, later tilted due to active folding. The terrace deposits are mainly composed of rounded sandstone cobbles with interstitial gravely sand, capped by a fine-grain soil, 0.5-4 m thick, interpreted as flood overbank deposits. Earlier studies lead to large age discrepancies with two OSL quartz ages in the order of 20 ka and three ^{10}Be exposure ages from ~105 ka to ~400 ka based on deep depth-profiles.

In this study, we analyzed five OSL samples from a flight of four terraces, labeled as PK6c, PK6b, PK5 and PK4 in ascending order. In the dearth of sand lenses, we sampled interstitial sand at 3-4 m depth in order to reach non-weathered sediment. For each sampled site we performed both BGSL on quartz grains and post-IR IRSL on K-feldspar grains, targeting the 100-250-micron fraction of the grains. New ^{10}Be radionuclide depth-profiles down to 3.5-m depth were collected at two sites, one on terrace PK6c, at the same outcrop as the OSL sample, and the other on terrace PK3. The OSL measurements were performed on Risø readers using single-aliquot regenerative (SAR) protocols. To test the suitability of the SAR protocols we did pre-heat, dose recovery and IR tests for quartz, and dose recovery test, residual dose measurements and fading measurements for post-IR IRSL at 225°C or 290°C on K-feldspars. Dose rates were calculated from the activities of ^{40}K and decay products of the uranium and thorium series, which were measured by gamma-ray spectrometry on 800-900 g of bulk sediment samples. We obtained dose rates ranging from 2.5 to 3.0 Gy/ka for quartz and 4.0 to 4.8 Gy/ka for K-feldspars.

The BGSL ages from quartz increase from 41 ± 4 ka on the lowest terrace PK6c to 54 ± 5 ka on PK4, as expected from geomorphology. These ages are clearly below saturation as indicated by their $2D_0$ values. Similarly, the post-IR IRSL K-feldspar age estimates, corrected for anomalous fading, also increase with the relative elevation of the terraces. However, they are significantly older than the quartz ages, and range from ~130 ka on PK6c to ~160 ka on PK4, with the samples from PK6c, and possibly PK4, close to saturation. Earlier ^{10}Be exposure ages, as well as our new preliminary ^{10}Be model ages, tend to support the post-IR IRSL ages rather than the quartz ages. On-going work focuses on the mineralogical properties of the grains and on the bleaching efficiency for both BGSL on quartz grains and post-IR IRSL on K-feldspar grains of samples from the modern Choushui riverbed and may provide new insights to determine which age set is more reliable.

Characteristics of POSL signals of quartz and feldspars with green light stimulation

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The blue LEDs stimulated pulsed OSL (POSL) signal, referring to PBLSL signal, has been employed to determine equivalent dose (D_e) for quartz extracts with feldspar contamination during the last decade. In spite of its general success, the PBLSL signal still suffers from the interference of signals from feldspars, and is difficult to apply to dim quartz aliquots. The POSL signal resulting from the green light stimulation, referring to PGLSL, for K-feldspar is characterized by much shorter relaxation time, although the signal-to-noise ratio is worse than the PBLSL signal. Therefore, the PGLSL signal makes it possible to gate the POSL signal closer to the switch off of the stimulation source, which may relieve the loss of signal during the off-period. In this study, we investigate the characteristics of PBLSL and PGLSL signals of quartz and K-feldspar samples from a variety of provenances to evaluate the feasibility of using PGLSL signal as an alternative for D_e determination. The time constant for building up and relaxation of BLSL and GLSL signals of both minerals are determined by time resolved OSL measurements to investigate the temporal evolution of relative contribution of quartz and K-feldspar in the mixed samples. The effect of IR stimulation, on and off period, integration interval on the intensities and quartz signal contribution are also investigated for the PBLSL and PGLSL signals. Finally, the performance of the PGLSL signal on reducing the feldspar contamination and its appropriateness to dim samples are evaluated, with comparison to the PBLSL signal.

OSL-based chronology of sand dunes in Golestan Province, Northern Iran with implications on Late Pleistocene-Early Holocene history of the Caspian Sea

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The development of aeolian deposits, such as dune and loess, strongly depends on climate conditions and sediment availability. Hence, these deposits can provide valuable information about palaeoatmospheric circulation, wind activity, palaeoclimate and landscape evolution. Aeolian deposits are widespread in Golestan Province, in Northern Iran. The loess deposits are dominant in the north-east part of the province, and are part of the Eurasian loess belt. In addition to the loess deposits, several isolated dunes have been developed on the flat lowland of the Gorgan Plain, which spreads between the Caspian Sea (West), the Koppeh Dagh and Alborz Mountains (East and South) and the Karakum desert (North). While the loess chronology in this area is relatively well constrained (>20 ka) [1], the formation time of the sand dunes remains largely overlooked, despite their potential to provide valuable information in terms of palaeoclimate conditions and Caspian Sea level reconstruction. In this study, we provide the first reconstruction of dune evolution in the Golestan Province, based on sedimentological description, high resolution granulometric analysis and optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating. Preliminary measurements on the quartz samples showed severe feldspar contamination, probably due to feldspar inclusion within quartz grains. In order to establish a reliable luminescence chronology, we applied different luminescence dating approaches, including quartz post-infrared (IR) pulsed OSL (Post-IR POSL) and K-feldspar post-infrared (IR) infrared stimulated luminescence (IRSL) (pIRIR) measurements. The quartz POSL signal is generally characterized by a dim luminescence and resulting broad equivalent dose (D_e) distributions with relatively high overdispersion value (~40%). Since the feldspar pIRIR₁₅₀ analysis results more uniform D_e and exhibits higher luminescence signal intensities, the pIRIR₁₅₀ ages are used for interpretation.

Dune geomorphology, grain size distributions and sedimentological investigations indicate a clear influence of the Caspian coast environment on the sediment supplies for dune development, in addition to the probable input from nearby fluvial systems. OSL dating of the studied dunes indicates that dunes accreted in less than few thousand years and pIRIR₁₅₀ ages clustered around 10 ka, reflecting a relatively rapid aggradation during the Late Pleistocene-Early Holocene transition. The dunes accretion likely occurred under arid palaeoclimate conditions with strong wind activity, and reflects a quick regression of the Caspian Sea during the Late Pleistocene-Early Holocene transition, coinciding with the so-called Mangyshlak regression phase. This is consistent with the apparent spatial and temporal pattern of the dated dunes, which, within age uncertainty, suggests that the older dunes are located further inland compared to the younger ones. This configuration is characteristic of a low sea level model which is associated with the gradually wider exposure of shelf area to wind activity resulting in shore progradation.

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Analysing the stability of Luminescence signal of samples of known Ancient and modern ages

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To examine the stability of luminescence signal, luminescence signals of quartz and feldspars grains from ancient and modern sediments of diverse depositional environments were studied using, a) blue light stimulated, b) infrared stimulated and c) post infrared-infrared stimulated luminescence (BLSL, IRSL₅₀ and pIR-IRSL₂₉₀). These luminescence signals were analysed to understand the extremum limits of ages that can be obtained using these signals. The environmental dose rate in these samples ranged from 1.5 Gy/ka to 3 Gy/ka and the depositional environments varied from palaeofan / fluvial settings of Siwaliks in the foothills of Himalaya, tsunami lain sands from Peninsular India and aeolian sands from the Thar Desert. The Siwalik samples had some age controls based on paleomagnetic data and the paleomagnetic ages ranged from 1.7 – 5.24 Ma.

Observations from this study are:

1. BLSL Quartz signal based equilibrium dose ranged from 80 Gy to 150 Gy and the saturation dose ranged from 150 Gy to 180 Gy. These suggest an age upper limit of 100 ka.
2. Fading corrected [1, 2] IRSL₅₀ equilibrium ranged from 600 Gy to 1100 Gy, and the saturation dose ranged from 1000 Gy to 1350 Gy. These correspond to ages in the range 350 ka to 700 ka for samples with geological antiquity of 1.7 Ma to 5.24 Ma.
3. Fading corrected pIR-IRSL₂₉₀ equilibrium ranges from 1350 – 2850 Gy. The saturation dose was ~ 2800 Gy. These imply ages from 800 ka to 1.3 Ma for samples with ages in the range 1.7 Ma to 5.4 Ma.
4. The g-values for pIR-IRSL₂₉₀ signal ranged from 1 – 3 %/decade and were higher than 1-1.5 %/decade reported so far. The g-values of IRSL₅₀ ranged from 4.3 – 7.2 %/decade [1, 2].
5. A sample from the surface of dunes (expected to have a near zero age) shown equivalent dose of 1.5 Gy for quartz BLSL and 2.5 Gy for IRSL₅₀ and 3.5 Gy for pIR-IRSL₂₉₀ respectively. This suggests bleachability of IRSL₅₀ is only marginally higher than pIR-IRSL₂₉₀. Similar results from Tsunami sands were seen.

Fading uncorrected IRSL₅₀ ages when plotted against pIR-IRSL₂₉₀ ages could be fitted to a single saturating exponential and this correlation could provide a first order correction to existing IRSL ages up to a few hundred ka based on the best fit line between the two sets of values. A comparison of the pIRIRSL ages with geological ages suggests an upper limit of a million years in current dose environments.

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News from Freiberg Instruments – Some recent developments

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The concept of the lexsyg research luminescence reader [1], with the separation of sample storage and measurement chamber, allows every sample treatment to be performed at elevated temperatures, because the sample is located on the heater plate throughout the entire measurement/treatment sequence. This also allows irradiations with α -, β - or x-rays at temperatures up to 300°C. Recently, a special arm with two sample positions, one on each side, has been developed. This allows standard heating operation between room temperature and 710°C on one side, and cooling of the sample below room temperature on the other side. As no cooling fluid or gas is required, the thermoelectric cooling unit enables routine high-throughput irradiations and luminescence measurements at low temperatures in the range of -50 to 100 °C.

Minor geometric changes by the rotation of the disc/cup holding the sample are negligible for most luminescence measurements. This is, however, not the case in radiofluorescence of, e.g. K-feldspar, where the identical geometry has to be maintained during the entire procedure. Improvements in the bearing of the rotational arm now minimize disc rotations in lexsyg research systems to a level even negligible in radiofluorescence.

A software plugin (SARPI) is part of the LexStudio2 software for operating any lexsyg device. It is designed to aid in the generation of standard SAR measurement sequences in order to minimize errors due to operator mistakes. The analysis of SAR data in the software LexEva2 is based on the R-package 'luminescence' and now also includes results from dose modelling. Equivalent doses can also be obtained from multiple aliquot additive and regeneration data.

For age calculation an entirely revised version of the ADELE code [2] has been designed. The platform independent software calculates effective dose rates from element concentrations, activity values or dose-rate data. ADELE is able to consider cases of complex radiation fields, like layered geometries, as well as situations showing time dependent dose rates, like changing moisture contents or radioactive disequilibria.

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ESR dating of quartz from the Luochuan site, Chinese loess plateau: A comparison with independent age control

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The accuracy of quartz electron spin resonance (ESR) dating using the Ti centre was tested through a comparison of the ESR ages of loess from the Luochuan site, Chinese loess plateau, with reference ages. The single aliquot regenerative dose (SAR) protocol was used to calculate the equivalent dose (D_e) values of five samples, with expected ages ranging from 28.5 ± 2.9 ka (L1) to 646 ± 65 ka (L6). The ages were then corrected for thermal signal loss, using the lifetime of the Ti centre, $\sim 1.7 \times 10^6$ years, previously calculated for a sample from the same site. The apparent ages range from 59.4 ± 3.6 ka to 517 ± 34 ka. For the youngest two samples ages are overestimated compared to the expected ages, which is presumably caused by incomplete signal resetting before burial. The apparent age of the oldest sample shows an age underestimation of $\sim 20\%$, but after thermal signal loss from the Ti centre is corrected for, the age is consistent with the reference age. Both apparent and corrected ages of L3 and L4 are in good agreement with independent age control. We show, that with careful consideration of the thermal stability and bleachability of samples, reliable age calculation using the Ti centre is possible.

Studies of standard growth curve (SGC) for MET-pIRIR signals from K-feldspar grains from the Nihewan Basin, north China

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As one of the most important regions for early human occupation in East Asia, the Nihewan Basin in north China is well-known for an abundance of archaeological sites with ages spanning the last 2 Ma. Because of many sites have no reliable ages, it is necessary to build a chronology framework to provide an age context for them. In this study, standard growth curves were investigated using both multiple-aliquot regenerative-dose (MAR) and single-aliquot regenerative-dose (SAR) procedures based on the multiple-elevated-temperature post-IR IRSL (MET-pIRIR) signals from K-feldspar [1, 2, 3]. Both the SAR and MAR SGCs were normalised using the signal induced by a regenerative dose of 373 Gy, in order to compare their shapes. For the 290 °C IRSL signal, which demonstrate a negligible fading, the MAR and SAR SGCs are indistinguishable at low doses up to ~800 Gy, but start to diverge at higher doses (>800 Gy), with the MAR SGC reach a slightly higher saturation signal level than the SAR SGC. As a result, considerably different equivalent doses (D_e) are obtained at high doses. Results from repeated measurements of the same given dose indicate that the difference in the MAR and SAR SGC shape can be attributed to the initial sensitivity changes between the 'natural' and test doses. We tested the influence of preheat, size of normalisation dose and test doses to the initial sensitivity change. We found that the first preheat treatment may change the electron trapping probability and then affected subsequent sensitivity. The implication of our results for dating old samples is discussed.

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SAR-TA-OSL dating of samples with ages larger than 1Ma; the case study from Kula geopark, Manisa, Western Turkey

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Despite the adequate thermal stability of the fast OSL signal for dating back to a million years, experimental ages determined in the laboratory are well below this upper limit. Moreover, applications to independently dated sedimentary deposits from the last 200ka have yielded underestimated OSL ages [1]. Recently, in order to deal with these problems of age limit extension, the effective application of other alternative signals derived from trapped electrons has been acknowledged [1]. Thermally assisted OSL (TA-OSL) signal arising from traps with delocalization temperature higher than 500 °C, stands among these alternative signals [2]. For the case of quartz, a number of promising TA-OSL features were revealed, including the intense decaying signal after both natural and artificial irradiations, along with the corresponding dose response properties. Especially the characteristic dose, D_0 , at which saturation begins occurring, is almost one order of magnitude larger than the corresponding values for conventional OSL signals [2].

In the framework of the present study, the single aliquot regeneration SAR [3] protocol was applied, employing both the TA-OSL signal as well as the conventional OSL. The SAR TA-OSL protocol was applied in order to date different geological samples which were collected from the volcanic geopark of Kula, a protected area of geological heritage by UNESCO in Manisa, Western Turkey. All these samples were independently dated previously, based on their geological context, indicating ages ranging from 1 up to 2.5 Ma. The aims of the present work include (a) presenting for the first time in the literature ages over 1Ma obtained using the SAR TA-OSL, (b) comparing the SAR TA-OSL age results with those indirectly obtained based on the geological context, in order to study the feasibility of the SAR-TA-OSL technique, (c) discussing methodological concepts, in order to select the optimum protocol parameters, such as the test dose, the stimulation duration and the stimulation temperature applied and (d) assessing the bleaching ability of the TA-OSL signal.

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C-14, U-series and ESR/U-series dating of the Paleolithic site of Yumi Cave in the Three Gorges Region, southwest of China

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Yumi Cave (30°50'44.4"N, 109°38'09.2"E) is a newly discovered Paleolithic site in the Three Gorges region of the Yangtze River in the southwest of China^[1]. The excavations during 2012 and 2013 led to the discovery of a large number of paleolithic artifacts and faunal remains, attributed to the *Ailuropoda-Stegodon* fauna. The cave deposits are mainly composed of clay and limestone breccia, and divided into 18 archaeological layers from the top to the bottom (> 5 m thick). The artifacts were found in association with faunal remains consistently in the deposits, indicating that the hominin played an important role for the accumulation of faunal remains at Yumi Cave. A previous study suggests that the geological age of this site is in the range of ca. 400 ka to 8 ka, based on biostratigraphic information and U-series dating of a few fossil teeth and speleothem samples. In the present study, C-14, U-series and ESR/U-series methods are used to refine the Yumi Cave chronostratigraphy.

The C-14 method was applied to six samples (3 bones and 3 charcoal) collected from the depth from -20 to -145 cm. They yielded calibrated ages ranging from 14.1 ± 0.1 ka BP to 40.9 ± 0.6 ka BP, in agreement with the stratigraphy. The U-series method was used to date nine bone samples, 16 in-situ deposited secondary carbonates and 11 speleothem fragments, collected from the depth between -150 and -500 cm. The bone samples yielded ²³⁰Th/U ages in the range of 46.7 ± 0.2 ka BP and 112.7 ± 0.5 ka BP, and the in-situ deposited secondary carbonates yielded ages in the range of 40.2 ± 0.2 ka BP and 151.5 ± 1.9 ka BP. These ²³⁰Th/U ages can be seen as the minimum ages for the corresponding layers. On the contrary, the speleothem fragments fallen from the cave roof provided the maximum age estimates ranging from 62.7 ± 0.2 ka to beyond 500 ka. Seven herbivorous fossil teeth from different archaeological layers were dated by coupled ESR and U-series method. The ESR/U-series ages range from 69 ± 5 ka to 307 ± 32 ka, which are seen as the direct age estimates for the archaeological layers.

According to these C-14, U-series and ESR/U-series ages, the Layer 2 can be constrained between 14 and 63 ka, Layer 3 between 100 and 178 ka, Layer 5 between 100 – 250 ka, Layer 8 > 150 ka, Layer 10 – 11 between 195 and 260 ka, and Layer 13 – 15 < 290 ka. More sophisticated Bayesian analysis^[2] of these dating results is now under way.

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OSL dating of Upper Pleistocene sediments from Paleolithic sites in Andhra Pradesh, India

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Jwalapuram sites (JWP) in Andhra Pradesh, India are South Asian paleolithic sites. Although the chronology of JWP had been studied by Roberts et al. [1] and Haslam et al. [2], sediments above young tuff (YTT, ca. 77 ka) were not measured. This study measured sediments of JWP using OSL dating.

We collected five samples from two locations: JWP 1 and JWP 2. These locations are between JWP Locality 3 and 22. The five samples were taken from above the YTT layer. Three samples of JWP 1 were collected from the upper (sample 1), middle (sample 2), and lower (sample 3) locations. Two samples of JWP 2 were collected from the upper (sample 1) and lower (sample 3) locations. All samples were separated to 4–10 µm diameter by wet sieving in a water and acetone solution. To separate the quartz, these samples were immersed for 8 days in 20% hydrofluorosilicic acid. All OSL measurements were taken using an OSL/TL reader (NRL-99-OSTL2-KU; Neoark Corp.) [3] equipped with an array of 20 blue LEDs (465±15 nm). Irradiation was conducted using a small X-ray tube (dose rate 0.16 Gy/s) built into the OSL reader. Dose–response curves for Paleodose estimation were constructed using the single aliquot regenerative-dose (SAR) procedure. Annual doses were measured using a high-resolution gamma-ray spectrometer.

The Paleodose values and their errors for aliquots of each sample were estimated using a Monte Carlo method [4, 5]. The overdispersion values of 0 or 9.4% for each sample were obtained. All samples were well bleached. The Paleodoses of all samples were calculated using the central age model [6]. All OSL ages were ca. 27–42 ka. The OSL ages of five samples are stratigraphically coherent within the measurement error range.

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Study on the sedimentary sequence and dating of the land-ocean interaction zone in the north Jiangsu Plain

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The dating of sedimentary is a key scientific problem in quaternary studies. Coastal sediments are difficult to search for suitable materials for radiocarbon dating due to multiple transport and deposition. However, Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL) dating is record the last exposure time of sediment, which is expected to solve the dating problem of complex coastal sedimentary environment. Here we investigated GX profile sediments in the Gangxi town, about 30 kilometers northwest of the Yancheng city of north Jiangsu Plain. The evolution process of the sedimentary environment was restored through analysis of profile sediment characteristics, combined with AMS14C dating, OSL dating, particle size, geochemical elements and diatom data. The result indicated that the period from 14000 to 7680 cal a B.P. was lacustrine sedimentary environment; 7680-6960cal a B.P. was shallow marine sedimentary environment; 6960-6680 cal a B.P. was an interactive sedimentary environment of land (freshwater lake), sea (intertidal zone) and land (freshwater lake) because of frequent sea level fluctuations; 5960-1500 cal a B.P. was freshwater lacustrine sedimentary environment. Consequently, the combination of OSL dating and AMS14C dating can solve the problem of relatively accurate dating in complex coastal strata.

Application of OSL, LM-OSL and TL methods to heated quartz from historical building in Karakorum, Mongolia

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The Mongolian-German Karakorum Expedition (MDKE) excavated a Buddhist temple in Karakorum – the ancient capital of Mongolia [1] and the chronological sequence of the brick production has been conducted. In order to obtain precise OSL estimates which is especially important for young samples (< 5 Gy), we apply different luminescence methods (such as SAR-OSL, ramped SAR-OSL and SAR-TL) to heated quartz grains in order to test their convergence.

Fitting exponential functions to OSL decay curves revealed the presence of a distinct “medium” component [2], but as it has been seen from preheat tests, the fitting also revealed that at the preheat of 260 °C the slow component contributes as largest to the overall OSL signal. For these blue-grey colored brick samples, TL-SAR yielded higher D_e values than using SAR-OSL suggesting that

- (i) the past heating had been too low, i.e. the TL signal has not been fully reset or
- (ii) the D_e obtained using the medium OSL component underestimated the age.

However, the TL results obtained on blue-grey colored bricks from the central stupa yield dates which are consistent with the C14 dates obtained from identical stupas.

In addition, our results suggest that quartz LM-OSL sensitivity signals is a useful indicator to discriminate between red-colored and blue-grey colored bricks; and it can thus be used for provenance analysis to understand the technology at that site.

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Characteristics of violet and ultraviolet stimulated luminescence from quartz

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Violet stimulated luminescence (VSL) of quartz has previously been reported to potentially extend the dating range up to 1 million years (Ma) [1]. This is achieved by the higher energy of violet light (405 nm, 3.1 eV) when compared to the conventionally used blue light (470-458 nm, 2.6-2.7 eV), which can access deeper traps that saturate at higher doses [1]. Despite the potential of this method, few applications have been published due to difficulties in obtaining a reliable equivalent dose (D_e) for natural samples. To be able to distinguish between the signal from deep traps and that of the shallower, conventional blue stimulated luminescence (BSL) traps, a thorough bleaching of the BSL signal is required beforehand. Therefore, high-temperature preheat and blue-light bleach steps must be used [1,2,3,4]. Attempts in determining low natural doses (e.g., < 70 Gy) and dose recovery experiments appeared to be successful. However, an unsuitability of the existing VSL-SAR protocols to determine D_e for old samples has been reported. This is possibly due to sensitivity changes between the natural and regenerative doses, which lead to underestimations [4].

In this study, we present results on the characteristics of the post-blue VSL signal of sedimentary quartz. We also investigated the characteristics of ultraviolet (365 nm, 3.4 eV) stimulated luminescence (UVSL), based on photo-transferred thermoluminescence (PTTL). We tested the experimental conditions suitable for removing the BSL, especially the slow components. Additionally, the thermal stability of VSL and UVSL were studied. Finally, the implications of using VSL or UVSL for dating are discussed.

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Late Quaternary dune activity in the Thar Desert, India: an insight from OSL dating

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It is generally accepted that insolation driven changes in monsoon intensity have affected contraction and expansion of the Thar Desert, India during the late Quaternary, impacting on the construction and accumulation of aeolian landforms [1,2]. Observation of dune alignment using remotely sensed imagery has shown that regionally, dunes are closely aligned with the prevailing wind direction of the southwest monsoon system. Therefore, the Thar dune systems potentially provide a rich archive of past climatic and geomorphological change. Whilst a small number of studies have undertaken geochronological investigations of dunes using luminescence dating [2,3], studies have been sporadic and have tended to rely on older dating protocols. As a result, the temporal and spatial analyses of Thar dune accumulation histories and their comparison with growing multiproxy framework of past environmental dynamics become difficult.

To address this, systematic sampling of dune fields was carried out in different regions in the desert. Sites were selected to form a transect across the modern precipitation gradient, and linear and parabolic dune forms, which have a high sediment preservation potential, were targeted. Optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating was used to provide a chronological framework, with the aim of inferring dune sensitivity to palaeoenvironmental change, and the time scales over which they register and preserve the palaeoenvironmental record.

This study presents a suite of 60 quartz OSL ages, calculated using the double-SAR protocol [4]. The chronology demonstrates a dynamic aeolian environment in the Thar during the late Quaternary, as well as spatial and temporal variability in aeolian accumulation across the region. The majority of accumulation is recorded after the Last Glacial Maximum, with the early Holocene identified as a phase of intensive and widespread accumulation, indicating that relatively more arid and windy conditions were prevalent during this period. OSL ages also show major phases during the mid-Holocene and within the last millennia, suggesting that potential drivers of dune mobility in the last century include a strong anthropogenic dimension [5]. The study concludes that a strategic approach to sampling coupled with robust dating protocols allow the scope for a more complex chronology to be identified and subsequently enhance our understanding of dunefield development.

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Luminescence dating on ceramic in Nuomuhong site in the Tibetan Plateau

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As a daily utensil and artefact used since the Late Glacial Maximum ^[1], pottery is direct evidence of human activities. A large number of ceramics were found in the Tibetan Plateau. The ages of most ceramics were determined according to the conventional method such as culture characteristics and radiocarbon dating on the charcoal or bones from the same cultural layer, but lack of the chronological data from the ceramic itself. Sometimes, due to the 'old wood' effect, the radiocarbon dating results may not accurately reflect the true age of human behaviour ^[2]. In addition, some type of pottery was used over a certain culture period. E.g., Dong et al. found a large amount of sand tempered brown ceramics in the Yushu autonomous prefecture, and the ages of these sites were thought to be continued to the historical period ^[3]. Therefore, it may be unreliable to judge the age of ceramic based solely on its cultural characteristics. In response to this problem, sand tempered grey ceramics in Nomuhong, were selected to determine the ages of five ceramics by using the optically stimulate luminescence dating in the Talitaliha site. The reliability of the OSL dating is verified through and the comparing with the 6 independent radiocarbon ages including 3 charcoal and 3 bones from the same cultural layer. The result shows that luminescence on ceramic have a good agreement with the ¹⁴C dating. Combined with previous studies, the range of NMH human activity is 3800-2900 Cal BP, suggesting that prehistoric human has conquered this region which is extremely arid now.

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Residual dose of post-IR IRSL of K-feldspar in modern and Holocene beach–shoreface sands, Pacific coast of eastern Japan

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Infrared stimulated luminescence (IRSL) and post-IR IRSL (pIRIR) of K-feldspar are harder to bleach than quartz optically-stimulated luminescence (OSL), and likely lead to overestimate of sediment date. However, residual doses of modern sediments have not been determined systematically, hindering their strict estimate and thus reliable application of K-feldspar IRSL and pIRIR dating to various environments. This is especially critical for Japan's active tectonic margin as quartz grains from young orogens are dim and there is extensive distribution of coastal and shallow-marine sediments since the middle Pleistocene to date for characterizing palaeo-environmental changes.

We assessed the magnitude of residual dose of K-feldspar coarse grains (180–250 μm in diameter) extracted from modern and Holocene beach–shoreface sands along the Pacific coast at Kujukuri, eastern Japan. In IRSL₅₀, modern foreshore and shoreface sands, obtained from the subaerial beach to lower shoreface 34 m deep, show residual doses < 0.2 Gy, which correspond to age overestimate of only several decades assuming the average annual dose in the area (2.5 Gy/ka). pIRIR_{50/150} is characterized by residual doses of 1–3 Gy, equivalent to 400 to 1300 years overestimate. Residual doses of pIRIR_{50/290} are up to 30 Gy, suggesting possible overestimate by >10000 years. For each signal, shoreface sands show no correlation of residual dose with the water depth. In contrast, one sample from foreshore shows lower residual doses of pIRIR_{50/150} and pIRIR_{50/290} than shoreface sands, suggesting that sustained subaerial sunlight bleaching appears to diminish the difficult-to-bleach component of these signals.

A shoaling-upward beach-shoreface succession recognized in a sediment core in the Kujukuri strand plain reveals concordant results with modern sands. The succession is dated younger than 2400 years by radiocarbon dating. Fading-corrected IR₅₀ ages agree well with or even slightly younger than expected ages, indicating that the residual dose is ignorable. In contrast, corrected pIRIR_{50/150} and pIRIR_{50/290} ages show overestimates of 700–1300 years and 9000–12000 years, respectively, as also expected from modern sands.

These results show IR₅₀ is generally well-bleached even in the underwater environment up to 34 m deep off the Pacific coast at Kujukuri or sands are extensively circulated between the nearshore and deeper water so that residual IR₅₀ is not accumulated much before the deposition. So far, IR₅₀ appears to be the best signal for dating Holocene sand in this area and pIRIR_{50/290} is likely to retain a residual dose that is critical even for distinguishing sub-stages in the Last interglacial period (Marine Isotope Stages 5a, 5c, and 5e). pIRIR_{50/150} may have an advantage in strictly dating the late Pleistocene coastal deposits if associated with a sufficiently low fading rate.

The effect of the fracture by shallow-fault movement on ESR signals of simulated-fault gouge

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Fault dating by Electron Spin Resonance (ESR) is a method to determine the age of fault movement. This method focuses on ESR signal, which is an unpaired electron in a defect, in fault materials and has two hypotheses to determine the age of fault: increase of ESR intensity, which is the number of unpaired electrons in defects, by irradiation with time and zeroing, which means ESR intensity decrease to zero, by fault movement [1]. However, we have not clarified totally the principle of zeroing [2]. Particularly, there are different results in previous studies on the effect of fracture (one of the causes of zeroing [1]) [e.g., 1-3]. Therefore, to reveal the relationship between ESR signals and fracture with special emphasis on whether shallow-fault movement gives rise to zeroing, we re-examined the relationship between them using a low-speed rotary shear apparatus.

The quartz powder supplied by APPIE, Japan, was used for samples of simulated fault gouges. The powder was made by crushed quartz sand ($\phi = 45\text{-}300\ \mu\text{m}$) composed of more than 95 wt% SiO_2 and a trace amount of impurities. The layer of the powder with a thickness of 1.4-1.6 mm was sheared between brass forcing blocks in a rotary shear apparatus, Tohoku University. The inside and outside diameters of the brass were 20 mm and 30 mm, respectively. So slip rate was 0.76 mm/s at the diameter of 25 mm. The displacement was changed from 0 to 1.4 m. The normal stress was kept constant at 0.98 MPa. After shearing, a sample was divided into halves for the measurement of ESR intensity and SEM observations. ESR measurement condition was determined to set similar to previous researches [e.g., 1, 4].

ESR intensity of E_1' center ($\equiv\text{Si}\bullet$) for sheared samples increased up to 120% compared with the starting materials, and linearly increased with displacement to about 0.85 m. Then it became constant with further displacement over 0.85 m. From SEM observations, we confirmed grain size reduction of simulated fault gouge by brittle fracture and mixing with small amount of brass. Previous researches [1, 4] reported that mixing of iron particles used in the apparatus to quartz sands decreases the ESR intensity. On the other hand, in this study, mixing of brass particle did not change the shape of ESR spectrum or increase the ESR intensity of quartz powder, and the local temperature rise [5] on the surface was estimated to be negligibly small (about 60 degrees). So the effect of frictional heating on ESR signals is much lower than in [1]. Therefore, the brittle fracture causes the change of ESR intensity, but shallow-fault movement can't cause zeroing. In the future, we have to research the other factors of zeroing without frictional heating.

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Single grain OSL study of heated and unheated quartz from Khutagt Uul Mountains, Orkhon valley, Mongolia

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Archaeological research in Orkhon Valley (Mongolia) has recently concentrated on numerous archaeological burials in the Khutag Uul Mountains [1], where several tombs have been associated with human activities from the nomadic Empire of the Xiongnu period (209 BC to the 2nd century AD) and from the Turk period (552 – 745 AD). In this work we study the luminescence characteristics of heated quartz (extracted from a pottery) and unheated quartz (extracted from the embedded sediment) from the same archaeological context.

Single grain quartz OSL showed that the relative scatter in D_e is substantially larger for the sediment sample (OD of 122%) than for the heated sample (OD of 12%). We think that the scatter in D_e for sediment sample is due to the following: (i). grain-to-grain variations in luminescence properties; (ii) heterogeneous bleaching of grains, and (iii) post-depositional mixing of grains from different sources [2]. In contrast, the heated quartz sample is characterized by (i) homogeneous bleaching of grains during manufacturing, negligible grain-to-grain variations in luminescence properties. We applied single grain OSL, which enabled us to distinguish grains that were well bleached at time of deposition from those that were incomplete bleached or from all mixed-age deposits. To reveal post-depositional mixing due to human activities, we applied different statistical models such as FMM and MAM [3] to the single grain dose distributions.

In addition, the OSL characteristics of the individual grains will be analyzed in view of various factors, such as statistical uncertainty due to photon counting and instrumental uncertainties to determine D_e . The grain-grain variations in the luminescence signal intensity, as well as the presence of fast, medium and slow components have been determined using LM-OSL measurements.

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Towards developing residual dose corrections in electron spin resonance (ESR) dating of sediments: on the equivalent doses obtained for young sedimentary samples using a multiple centre electron spin resonance dating approach

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Despite the fact that optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) and electron spin resonance (ESR) are both trapped charge dating methods that can be applied for obtaining chronologies for sediment deposition relying on the same resetting event (last exposure to sunlight) and by making use of the same material (quartz grains), these methods have rarely been the subject of age intercomparisons. OSL is usually employed for deposits whose chronologies do not exceed ages of ~200-300 ka, its main limitation being dictated by the saturation of the signals, while ESR is primarily used to date older sediments.

While the main ESR signals used for dating (Al-hole and titanium) display higher saturation characteristics, it is well known that their bleaching properties and potential residual signals are not very well characterised and quantified [1]. For testing the resetting of the signals used for dating, making use of a multiple centre approach was proposed and recently reinforced [2, 3].

Here we present the results of the application of the multiple centre ESR dating approach using Al-hole and titanium signals of quartz on young (< 50 ka) sedimentary samples (loess and sand) of different grain sizes (fine quartz of 4-11 µm, and coarse quartz of 63-90; 90-125; 125-180 and 180-212 µm, respectively) that have been previously securely and independently dated using OSL. While we confirm the well known fact that titanium signals are more easily bleached, our initial results show that Holocene aeolian samples may display Al-hole signals of a magnitude that translates into equivalent doses amounting to hundreds of Grays. As such, performing residual corrections is mandatory. Here, we test the use of modern analogues (Holocene samples) for performing residual dose corrections for older loess samples along with investigating the dependence of the magnitude of residual ESR signals as function of previous given dose. The results support our previous suggestion that coarse grains are to be preferred in ESR dating [4] and emphasize on the importance of performing residual dose corrections even when conducting multiple centre equivalent dose measurement approaches.

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Dose response of the E_1' center in quartz

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The E_1' center is one of the most common paramagnetic defects observed by electron spin resonance (ESR) in natural quartz, the formation of which is, however, quite complicated. It was shown that the increase of the ESR intensity of the E_1' center on heating is correlated with the decay of the Al center in quartz [1], which is consistent with the electronic process proposed [2] that the holes released from the Al center is trapped by the neutral oxygen vacancies with two electrons to combine with one of those electrons to form the E_1' center with an unpaired electron. It was pointed out [3] that the contribution of the counterfeit signal makes the E_1' center look having dose response to the gamma rays and look useful for dating, therefore, it is not recommended to use the E_1' center as other ESR signals used for dating. The observed intensity depends on two factors, the number of oxygen vacancies, the precursor of the E_1' center, and how much fraction of them are in paramagnetic.

It was shown [4] that the oxygen vacancies, the precursor of the E_1' center, are formed by gamma rays with very low efficiency, and how it turns paramagnetic on heating. However, the dose response of the "real" E_1' center simply by gamma ray irradiation has never been reported. In the present paper, the dose response of the E_1' center will be reported in the dose range of several hundred Gy after removing the contribution of the counterfeit signal.

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Intra-laboratory comparison of different experimental setups: another step further in the standardization of the ESR dating method applied to quartz grains

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Electron Spin Resonance (ESR) dating is a powerful method with a wide range of applications in Geosciences and in Archaeology. However, compared to other more established numerical dating methods such as Radiocarbon, Uranium-series, Ar-Ar or Luminescence dating, ESR suffers from a lack of standardization among the different laboratories around the world, not only in the analytical procedures employed, but also in the reporting of dating results and methodology. This is undoubtedly a major limiting factor for the development and wide recognition of the ESR dating method within the scientific community.

A few decades ago, some major inter-laboratory comparison studies have been focused on ESR dating of calcite or corals. In contrast, such attempts have never been reported so far in the case of ESR dating applied to optically bleached quartz grains since the first dating study published by Yokoyama et al. [1], while the repeatability of the ESR measurements of Al- and Ti-centres performed at low temperature (<100 K) is significantly more challenging.

In the recent years, part of our investigation has been centred on improving the reliability and accuracy of the ESR method applied to quartz grains, by identifying some of the main sources of uncertainty in the dating process. For example, a special attention has been paid to the selection of the correct fitting functions and to the evaluation of the impact of temperature on ESR intensity measurements and repeatability [2,3]. More recently, the definition of some minimum requirements for reporting ESR dating results and methodology based on quartz grains dating has also been proposed [4].

In the line of this ongoing investigation, we evaluate here the impact of the experimental setup on the ESR measurements and dose evaluation. Repeated measurements of quartz samples were performed at CENIEH, Spain, using two different Bruker spectrometers (EMXmicro and Elexsys E500) and resonators (standard rectangular ER 4102ST and cylindrical Super High QE cavities). Their performance in terms of sensibility, measurement repeatability and dose determination is presented here. The results of this work will enable to evaluate the potential impact of different experimental setups (as it is almost always the case among different ESR dating laboratories) on the dose evaluation, which is essential for a future standardization of the ESR dating method applied to optically bleached quartz grains.

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Application of long time artificial optical bleaching of the E1 ' center to sediment provenance tracing

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Three quartz samples extracted from different origins were collected for ESR evaluation to appreciate the optical bleaching kinetics of the E1 ' center in a long time scale. The results show that the E1 ' center increased at beginning and decreased at the end as previous researches have predicted. However, after exposure of about 400 hours to artificial sunlight, the E1 ' center were bleached to a steady increasing level, about 2.5 times of its natural level, and the increase level also exhibit a small variability among different sample origins. The constant increasing level provide a solid evidence for the potential use of the natural signal intensities of quartz E1 ' center in tracing sediment provenance. However, new convenient indication shed light on the possible use of the E1 ' center for ESR sediment dating remains confusion.

Can we recover the thermal history of K-feldspars by measuring their IRSL signals?

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The information of tectonic and surface processes embeds in the thermal history of minerals, which is a key window for investigating geodynamics. The accumulation of luminescence signals in minerals is determined by both the temporally varying radiation dose and ambient temperature. Therefore, the mineral luminescence signals are employed for subjects related to temperature, such as ore prospecting, paleo-firing temperature as well as luminescence thermochronology. As we know, luminescence thermochronology is used to invert the history of rock temperature change due to surface denudation processes. An implicit assumption of this kind of study is that the charge trapping process at high temperature in rocks is the same as that at room temperature for laboratory irradiation, however, it has not been verified so far. In this study, we employ several K-feldspar specimens to test whether the known temperature of laboratory irradiation could be recovered by using the procedures to invert the rock cooling history. The completely bleached K-feldspar aliquots are irradiated at elevated temperature to mimic the radiation environment in nature. The saturation ratios, characteristic saturation dose, trap depth parameters as well as fading rates of various IRSL signals are measured. Finally, the temperature of irradiation is inverted and compared with the known irradiation temperatures to evaluate whether the prescribed thermal history could be recovered.

Luminescence chronology of the Yellow River terraces in the Heiyukou area of the Jinshaan Gorge, China

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The Yellow River flows along the northern and northeastern margins of the Ordos Plateau, and cuts through the eastern plateau from north to south, resulting in the formation of the Jinshaan Canyon limited to the reach from Lamawan to Yumenkou, and the canyon links the Weihe graben and the Hetao graben in the middle reach of the Yellow River. A series of strath terraces have been developed along the banks of the canyon, and the fluvial terrace deposits are covered by loess with various thicknesses. One of the key issues concerning the geomorphological evolution of the river is to accurately determine the formation age of the terraces along the banks of the river. In this study, six strath terraces (T2-E (T2-W), T3, T4, T5, T6 and T7) in the Heiyukou area (38°32'36.34"N, 110°54'25.88"E) were recognized, and terrace deposits were collected for optical dating. In order to find out which procedure are suitable for equivalent doses, the luminescence properties of the quartz and feldspar extracts from the samples from the T2 terrace were first thoroughly investigated[1]. Based on these results, the experimental conditions and procedures for De measurements were determined, and used for dating the other terrace deposits.

The single-aliquot regeneration dose protocol was used to date fine-grained and coarse-grained quartz of 15 samples from other strath terraces. We define the OSL ages of the samples from the bottom of the terrace deposits as the formation age of the terraces. Therefore, the formation ages of T2-W, T3 and T4 are 69.7 ± 3.7 ka, 75.5 ± 4.0 ka and 107.7 ± 3.9 ka, respectively. Although the T5, T6 and T7 terraces were dated to about 140, 128, and 160 ka, respectively, the loess/paloesol sequences and red clay overlying the fluvial deposits indicate that the burial ages of these dated quartz samples are much underestimated, the formation ages should be much larger than these OSL age values.

Based on the heights of strath surface above the modern Yellow River level and the strath formation ages, the mean river incision rate between different terrace levels were calculated to be 0.25 mm/yr for the period between ~107 and ~75 ka, 2.84 mm/yr between ~75 and ~69 ka, 0.18 mm/yr between ~69 ka and present, respectively. The river incision rates in this area may reflect the uplift rate of the Ordos block in different periods. The terrace formation is influenced by tectonic uplift. The increase of incision rate during 75 to 69 ka may be related to the regression rate of knickpoint.

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The bleaching of different K-feldspar pIRIR signals of source materials of lacustrine sediment- a case study from Bosten lake basin in arid central Asia

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K-feldspar post-infrared infrared stimulated luminescence (pIRIR) dating provide an alternative methods to date late Quaternary samples that quartz OSL signal is insensitive or/and saturated. K-feldspar pIRIR dating has been widely applied to eolian deposit, but still limited to employ to lacustrine deposit because of the lack of assessment of bleaching related to the slow resetting of pIRIR signal comparing to that of quartz OSL signal. In this study, Different modern surface samples of the potential sources for lacustrine sediments were collected from eolian sand dunes, fluvial deposit at different parts of main tributary, and alluvial fans in Bosten Lake drainage basin in southern Tianshan Mountains of arid Central Asia. The equivalent doses and residual doses of K-feldspar pIR₅₀IR₁₇₀, pIR₅₀IR₂₉₀ and pIR₂₀₀IR₂₉₀ signal for these modern analogue samples were measured. Our results show that: (1) K-feldspar pIRIR residual doses for samples from different source have shown a large difference. (2) The pIR₅₀IR₂₉₀ residual age for alluvial, fluvial and eolian modern analogues are 40-6, 6-3, and 2-1 ka, respectively, indicating the residual dose of modern analogue samples are related to sediment type. The residual age of pIR₂₀₀IR₂₉₀ signal is two times to that of pIR₅₀IR₂₉₀ signal, while the residual age of pIR₅₀IR₁₇₀ signal is similar to that of pIR₅₀IR₂₉₀ signal for alluvial, fluvial and eolian modern analogues, respectively. (3) The coarse-grained K-feldspar of eolian and fluvial is likely well-bleached before deposited to the lake, while the coarse grained K-feldspar of alluvial is possible poor-bleached before deposited to the lake. (4) It may not be advisable to apply pIRIR dating utilizing different pIRIR signals to Holocene lacustrine samples mainly from fluvial and alluvial due to high residual dose. However, these residuals quickly become ignorable for samples mainly from eolian deposit (e.g., Using K-feldspar pIR₅₀IR₁₇₀ signal to date Holocene sample and using pIR₂₀₀IR₂₉₀ and pIR₅₀IR₂₉₀ signals to date Pleistocene samples).

Age and genesis of the alluvial fans in the Daqingshan Inner Mongolia, China

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Fluvial and alluvial deposits contain important archives of paleoclimate and tectonic events, but the related research level is insufficient because of the limitation of reliable age results [1]. Therefore, it's very important and meaningful to carry out the chronology research for better understanding the history of the tectonic activities and climatic evolution.

There are several alluvial fans formed in the front of Daqingshan in the Inner Mongolia during the Holocene. A few typical alluvial fan sections are identified in the Daqingshan, which is applied with AMS-14C and OSL dating to ensure relatively accurate age framework. Both of the results of two methods are in good agreement with the age of paleosol in peripheral region [2]. Our result shows that there are at least 3 period fans. To be specific, the lower fans yield the age of 11-8 ka BP, the middle fans yield the age of 8-4 ka BP, and the upper fans yield the age of 2 ka BP. Among them, the early Holocene fan is the widely distributed, which looks like single body coming from the Medaigou and Wanjiagou, the middle Holocene fans are distributed as one group along the southeast of Daqingshan, and the old Holocene can be only founded in some gullies. What's more, there are some depression deposits in the inter fans, which indicates the sedimentary response to warm and humid weather at that time. After carefully analyses on the ages of alluvial fans and comprehensive research on the regional records of the activity fault, paleoclimatic change and environmental evolution, we find the tectonic active played a significant role in controlling regional alluvial fans geomorphic evolutions even within the climate variations at some period in the Holocene.

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Luminescence dating of young sands from North Heishuiguo site in the Hexi Corridor of Northwest China

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The North Heishuiguo site is one of most important ancient cities in the Hexi Corridor of Northwest China. Historical document and archaeological investigation showed that this city was founded in the Tang Dynasty (618-907 AD) and abandoned in the middle Qing Dynasty (1644-1911 AD) [1]. It has been speculated that the abandonment of the North Heishuiguo was due to environment deterioration caused by aeolian desertification. However, convictive evidences for this hypothesis are still absent.

In this study, samples were collected from four drilling cores in the aeolian sand which accumulated alongside the city wall of the North Heishuiguo site for luminescence dating. Considering that these sample are very young (probably <500 years), equivalent dose will be determined using quartz OSL and feldspar pIRIR₁₅₀ signals [2] of coarse grains, respectively. The radionuclide concentrations for dose rate calculation will be measured by the neutron activation analysis (NAA) and ICP-MS/ICP-AES together. Then the ages derive from different methods will be cross-checked to confine the initiation and duration time of the aeolian sand formation alongside the city wall of the North Heishuiguo site. This study could provide sedimentological and chronological data for exploring the historical human-environment interaction in the Hexi Corridor.

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Establishing a chronological framework for the sediments of Yitang Lake in Dunhuang basin, northwest China

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Yitang Lake is located in Dunhuang basin on the north side of Altynian Mountain and Qilian Mountain, with extremely widely distributed sedimentary strata as an important carrier of climate and environmental change in the Kumtag desert region [1]. However, research into sediment deposition and climate change in this area is limited due to the lack of independent age control. In this study, we drilled and acquired nearly 300 m sediment cores from Yitang Lake in Dunhuang basin, the standard quartz SAR OSL and K-feldspar post-IR infrared (IR) stimulated luminescence (post-IR IRSL; pIRIR₂₉₀) [2,3] methods have been used to establish the chronology of the upper 50 m of the depositional sequence. The quartz OSL characteristics are satisfactory (no IR sensitivity, dominant fast component). For K-feldspar pIRIR, dose recovery tests were performed by adding different laboratory doses to natural samples, it was satisfactory up to ~600 Gy. Additionally, stability tests (first IR temperatures plateau and g-values) were performed. Our results show that quartz SAR OSL and K-feldspar pIRIR₂₉₀ ages are more or less indistinguishable from one another up to ~30 ka. Beyond this age, the K-feldspar pIRIR₂₉₀ ages increased systematically with deposition depth to ~400 ka. Based on our independently-dated luminescence ages, we observe a marked accumulation hiatus of lake sediments from ~30 to ~100 ka, may indicates the abrupt change of the regional sedimentary environment and relevant to the sediment supply, which potentially closely associated with the Asian aridification and driven by the growth and decay of northern hemisphere ice sheets, and this paleoclimate inference responded to the northwest inland drought trend under global climate change.

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Feasibility study of ESR dating about the fault active in carbonate rock area

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Active faults are widely distributed in China, and some active faults are distributed in carbonate rock area. Fewer materials can be used to measure the age of fault activity in carbonate rock area. Carbonate is the main substance. Thus, How to use carbonate to realize fault activity identification has become the focus of research.

Since the first attempt to date a stalactite by ESR^[1], natural carbonates have been the object of many studies. According to the principle of ESR dating, we know that whether the ESR signal of the tested substance can be bleached to zero or a stable residual value at the time of the last event is the key to obtain a reliable equivalent dose. So, the main purpose of the present work is to observe and compare the variation characteristics of carbonate ESR signal before and after fault activity.

During the fault activity, there is melting on the frictional surface of carbonate rock due to the heat produced by friction, and the thickness of the molten layer is about a few millimetres. In this study, we picked samples on the frictional surface and the carbonate rock of East foot fault of Jade Dragon Snow Mountain, Yunnan, China.

The samples were crushed into 100-200 μm grain size, and drying after cleaning with distilled water, and then divided into 200 mg aliquots. At the end, these aliquots have received additional gamma doses range from 0 to 1000 Gy using the ⁶⁰Co gamma source of Peking University. Generally, there are many ESR signal centers in carbonate^[2] but in our samples the signal of $g=2.0023$ responds well to absorbed dose and can be used in our study.

By observing and comparing the ESR signal characteristics of the friction surface and the carbonate rock samples, we find that the ESR signal of melt carbonate (after fault activity) is more weaker than carbonate rock (before fault activity). It show that the friction heat of the fault activity can reduce the ESR signal of the carbonate, which provides the feasibility to use the melt carbonate of friction surface to study the fault activity age.

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The necessity to check feldspar contamination on each aliquot for quartz OSL dating

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Due to the different growth curve shape of quartz and feldspar, the contamination of feldspar signals can change the shape of growth curve of quartz. Additionally, feldspar signals are difficult to be bleached and have anomalous fading, consequently, contamination of feldspar might cause age overestimation or underestimation of quartz OSL dating in different cases. As a result, researchers try to get pure quartz and check IRSL signal in quartz sample before dating. Usually, only a few aliquots are checked to determine whether the feldspar contamination is low enough to be ignored, and the acceptable ratio of IRSL to OSL signal is <10%. However, due to the high sensitivity of feldspar signal, the differences of feldspar signal amounts are quite large among each aliquot, especially for the small aliquots of coarser grains, which increase the possibility of serious feldspar contamination in some aliquots. The feldspar contamination could also be checked at the last cycle of Single Aliquot Regeneration (SAR) protocol on regenerated signals. However, this will cause underestimation of the IRSL signal contribution, because the regenerated OSL signals have increased a lot by the last cycle compared with the nature quartz OSL signal due to sensitivity change, but the IRSL signals keep stable. Worse more, if the high IRSL contamination are found at the last cycle, the time spent on this disk was wasted. Additionally, for the application of Standard Growth Curve (SGC), there is no IRSL check on each aliquot to ensure the purity of quartz signals. In this study, we propose a modified SAR protocol for quartz OSL dating to check the IRSL signals of each aliquot in earlier stages, i.e., to measure nature signal (Ln/Tn, step1-5: preheat – BSL₁₂₅ – Td – preheat – BSL₁₂₅) first, and then to do IR check (IRSL/BSL, step 6-9: Td – preheat – IRSL₁₂₅ – BSL₁₂₅). Then selection is made according to the IRSL/BSL values of each aliquot, and if the value is higher than about 0.05, this aliquot will be abandoned without further measurement of SAR or SGC. By the application of this method, more time could be saved, and the D_es could be more concentrated, which can accordingly increase the accuracy of dating results.

Luminescence dating and environmental implication of sand wedges from the south of Badain Jaran Desert

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Sand wedges form under the cold permafrost environment [1], and thus it can be used to recover the past climatic conditions, especially the temperature. In this study, we reported a series of sand wedges around the Mountains Mandela in the south of Badain Jaran Desert. These sand wedges formed over the alluvial gravels, and the fillings are mainly composed of aeolian sand. Three samples were collected to constrain the timing of the sand wedge formation from the study area. Quartz fractions will be extracted for optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating these samples. A set of routine tests on OSL characteristics such as preheat plateau test and dose recovery test would be carried out to validate the applicability of the selected measurement procedure; the resultant quartz OSL ages will also be confirmed by the counterpart k-feldspar luminescence dates for each sample, which can be determined by the post-IR IRSL protocols. Finally, the implication of these sand wedges on the permafrost distribution and the past temperature will be reconstructed and discussed.

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A luminescence chronology of Alpine meadow soil based on both Quartz OSL and K-feldspar pIRIR signals from Qinghai Lake basin Riyue Mountain

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The extensive alpine meadow soil distributed in Qinghai Lake basin plays a core role in local ecological system. Its formation and pedogenic process under different climate background is still unclear. Abundant paleoclimate records in Qinghai Lake have been reconstructed by Past Global Change scientists. Therefore, systematic dating on different soil genetic horizons can provide chronology of detailed pedogenic process. In this study, a luminescence chronology based on both quartz optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) and K-feldspar infrared stimulated luminescence (post-IR IRSL, pIRIR) signals was employed to determine age of the sand-sized (63-90 μm) fractions of the 12 samples from two alpine meadow soil profiles (RYS1 and RYS2) in the Qinghai Lake southeastern on the northeast fringe of the Qinghai-Tibetan Plateau for the first time. The results show that: 1. Luminescence chronology method is validated to be adaptable and reliable for dating alpine meadow soils. 2. The single aliquot regenerative dose protocol (SAR) is appropriate for equivalent dose (D_e) determinations of the alpine meadow soil; Luminescence characteristics show that the typical fast quartz fractions in the profiles of Riyue Mountain meadow soil were well bleached before deposition. 3. Anomalous fading test is essential to measure D_e of K-feldspar^[1]. The pIRIR₁₇₀ fading rate of this paper are stable ($0.69\pm 0.21\%/dec$ - $1.26\pm 0.13\%/dec$), and the anomalous fading effect can be ignored. 4. The coarse-grained quartz OSL ages and K-feldspar pIRIR ages of alpine meadow soil are in reliable agreement, it formed and developed mainly during the late Holocene (4-0 ka). The parental material is derived from aeolian deposits and follows the mode of aeolian dust aggradation in soil development^[2, 3]. Combined with the environmental records of this region during the late Holocene^[4], alpine meadow soil is deemed to be a product of relatively cold climate.

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The bleaching limits of feldspar IRSL and post-IR IRSL signals at various preheat temperatures and implications for dating

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The post-IR IRSL (pIRIR) techniques [1,2], has been intensively used for dating feldspars in the middle to late Quaternary. Two crucial aspects for accurate pIRIR dating are the stability and bleachability of the target signal. While higher-temperature pIRIR signals are more stable, they tend to exhibit higher residual doses (~tens of Gy) before burial, potentially causing severe age overestimation in young samples. Although it has been experimentally demonstrated that high-temperature pIRIR signals are increasingly difficult to bleach [3], the origin and the underlying mechanism of this residual signal is not yet understood. In this work, we further explore the lower limits of IRSL and pIRIR signals bleaching under various thermal treatment conditions, using a young loess sample with a known quartz OSL age of 6.3 ± 0.4 ka [4].

Aliquots were optically bleached in a solar simulator (SOL2) under full spectrum light for durations ranging from 10 min to 20 days; a control group was not bleached at all. The test-dose corrected luminescence (L_n/T_n) of both bleached and unbleached aliquots were obtained using the modified single-aliquot regenerative-dose (SAR) protocol described in Zhang et al. (2015), with the post-IR stimulation always 30°C below preheat temperatures, which varied between 180°C and 340°C.

The obtained bleaching curves demonstrably deviate from the power-law behavior as originally suggested by Kars et al. (2014), showing an appreciable slowing-down of the bleaching rate at long times, even for the lowest (180°C) preheat. After prolonged bleaching, all IR50 signals reach a plateau, while most of the pIRIR signals continue to decrease, although the existence of a pIRIR plateau is expected for even longer light exposures. Such a bleaching plateau may originate from either thermal transfer of charge from light-insensitive traps [5], or a competition between optical bleaching and UV excitation.

These results shed further light on the buildup of unbleachable IR and pIRIR components with time, and further supports the notion that young samples should be preferably dated using lower preheat and stimulation temperatures in the pIRIR protocol.

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Comparison of equivalent doses obtained from various post IR dating protocols for potassium rich feldspar samples

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Several protocols with post-infrared (pIR) stimulations were proposed for dating of potassium rich feldspar samples. The IR stimulated luminescence (pIR-IRSL) at elevated temperatures was measured for dating after pIR stimulation. It was claimed that the anomalous fading part of the pIR-IRSL signals has been removed after the treatments of pIR stimulation. There are many combinations of different treatments of pIR and the IRSL measurement conditions, because of changing in the stimulation temperatures and number of steps. Commonly used protocols are either two steps or multiple steps (MET).

Jingbian section is in the margin of Chinese Loess Plateau, adjacent to Mu Us desert. The loess samples have abundant grains between 100-200 μm , which is suitable for separation of potassium rich feldspar using heavy liquids. These samples are well bleached prior to deposition, bright, uniform. Therefore, they are ideal for comparative studies. 4 protocols have been applied to samples younger and older than 150 ka. These protocols include two steps single aliquot regenerative dose with IR stimulations at 50 and 290 °C (SAR pIRIR(50,290))^[1]; two steps with stimulations at 200 and 290 °C (SAR pIRIR(200,290))^{[2][3]}; and multiple steps with stimulations at 50,100,150,200 and 250 °C (SAR MET-pIRIR(250))^[4]; and multiple aliquots regenerative doses with multiple steps of IR stimulations (MAR MET-pIRIR (300))^[5]. The protocols were applied to the same sample separates for direct comparison of the equivalent doses (D_e). Little difference is found in D_e values for samples younger than paleosol S1, while, significant differences are observed for the older samples. The results indicate that caution should be taken in selecting the pIR-IRSL dating protocols for the loess samples older than ~150 ka.

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Sedimentary stratigraphy and chronology in the Linhe Depression of Hetao Basin in northern China since the late Middle Pleistocene

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Hetao Basin, deposited by thick Quaternary sediments, is a Cenozoic fault basin developed between the Ordos Block and the Yinshan Mountain. The migration of the Yellow River channel happened several times in this basin after the cutthrough of the river. The Quaternary sediments in the basin are multiple overlying of Yellow River channel sediments, lake sediments and pre-mountain alluvial fan sediments. Therefore, the Quaternary sediment in Hetao Basin records important events such as the development and filling process of the basin, the ancient channel shifting and the environmental evolution. The establishment of accurate chronological framework of Hetao Basin is of great significance for understanding the Quaternary sedimentary process and sedimentary environment changes in this area. In this paper, the OSL chronology and the sedimentary strata structure reflected by the lithology and particle size results from 6 drillings of QK1, QK3, QK5, WY1, WY2 and WY3 in the west of the Linhe depression were determined. And the layer boundaries in different times were systematically defined. In the area to the north of the Yellow River, the boundary between the upper Pleistocene and the Holocene layers is at the depth of 100-400 m, getting deeper from north to south and shallower from west to east; and the Holocene deposits are 5-20 m thick, becoming thicker from north to south as well. In the area to the south of the Yellow River, the upper Pleistocene and the Holocene layers are about 85 m and 5 m thick, respectively. It concluded that the spatial differentiation of the strata in Linhe depression since the late Middle Pleistocene is mainly related to the base topographic features and the sedimentary dynamics, and the tectonic activities. Especially, the river alluviation during the evolution of the Yellow River has an important influence on the strata formation in this region.

Luminescence dating of late Pleistocene lacustrine deposits in Badain Jaran desert, North China

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There still have controversies for the lakes evolution time during late Pleistocene in north China. Badain Jaran Desert (BJD) features the coexisting of lakes between megadunes; also lots of lacustrine relics could be found distributed widely inter-dune sand land. These lacustrine relics indicated the paleo lake evolution and the paleo environmental changes in the desert. In this study, one 3.9 m depth lacustrine deposits section was found in the southeastern BJD close to a modern lake Zongzegedan (ZZGD). The section is studied by using optical dating with both of quartz and K-feldspar grains. Quartz optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating shows that this paleolake was appeared in MIS3 stage, without the saturation of the OSL signals. On the other hand, the pIR₅₀IR₂₉₀ and MET-pIRIR dating results show that the paleolake was existed in MIS5 stage with also good luminescence characteristics. The further study suggested that the OSL signals from quartz grains in this section show thermal instability, which may lead to the age underestimation. So the reliable age of the existed paleolake should be in MIS5 during the lake Pleistocene, indicated that the relative humid environment in the desert during the period. The OSL dating by using quartz should be caution in this desert, especially for the 'older' samples.

Reliability of OSL dating alluvial-diluvial deposits in Northern Piedmont of the Hengshan Mountain

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Late Quaternary geomorphological types in northern piedmont of the Hengshan Mountain are mainly composed of alluvial-diluvial platform, river-gully terrace and alluvial-diluvial fans formed in the same period. Late Quaternary sediment types are mainly alluvial-diluvial deposits. With short transport times and the possibility of light exposure, the accuracy of OSL dating is challenging. In order to verify whether the OSL ages of alluvial-diluvial deposits are reliable we compared their ages and AMS¹⁴C dates. AMS¹⁴C dates constrain these OSL ages. Different sizes quartz extracted from alluvial-diluvial samples were measured using both single-grain and multi-grain SAR OSL techniques. The minimum-age model(MAM) was applied to dose distributions determination. Besides a few grains most grains probably were well bleached for dose distributions appeared to be narrow and close to symmetrical and only a few outliers at high doses. The environment dose rate results of these OSL samples are obtained by gamma-ray spectrometer with high purity germanium. Different sizes quartz OSL ages are indistinguishable from each other and consistent with AMS¹⁴C dates and stratigraphic sequence. From our study we conclude that different grains maybe come from the same source, alluvial-diluvial deposits in study area were bleached easily and can be accurately dated using quartz OSL. OSL technique is feasible in alluvial-diluvial deposits.

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Loess deposits OSL dating in Pingyin (Shandong) and their implications for climate changes in eastern China

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Paleoclimatic variation in Shandong loess, land-sea transition zone of lower reaches at Yellow River and the eastern Chinese Loess Plateau, is complex and the nature of these changes on sub-orbital scales remains unclear. Widespread loess documents at Pingyin (in Shandong province) provide records of paleoclimatic variation in East Asian monsoon region. However, these records are difficult to interpret due to a lack of robust high-resolution chronologies. Coarse-grained quartz SAR-OSL and K-feldspar pIRIR dating were utilized to date 27 samples from a ~8 m loess-paleosol sequence in Pingyin, Shandong. The reliability of quartz and K-feldspar ages were confirmed by internal checks of luminescence characteristics of the SAR OSL and pIR200IR290 signals, and calculated by comparison of quartz and feldspar ages. A high-resolution chronology for the loess-paleosol sequence, spanning 75-8 ka, in combination with climate proxies of magnetic susceptibility and grain-sizes demonstrate: (1) Resulting coarse quartz OSL and feldspar pIRIR290 ages are in good agreement since the last interglacial at Pingyin loess section. (2) The boundary of Holocene and Pleistocene is ~12 ka; the boundary of Glacial and Interglacial is ~65 ka. (3) A marked hiatus in the record is identified between ~30 ka and ~17 ka at the Pingyin site, this remained unrecognized in previous work. The Pingyin loess has been discontinued since 17 ka, which is possible a response to the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) warming with high temperature and heavy rainfall events in China.

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Luminescence signals from polymineral fine-grains in sediments from the Fengshuzui paleolithic site of Chishan Island, northern Hunan and their use for dating

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Recent archaeological excavation at Fengshuzui site (28°56'47"N, 112°17'22"E) of Chishan Island in northern Hunan, South China has uncovered a large number of Acheulean-like stone tools. Sediments at the site are very fine and strongly weathered. An early attempt of dating the site utilized fine-grained quartz and has resulted in stratigraphically consistent OSL ages in the range of 70-120 ka for five samples collected from four layers. Here we report a study which was specifically designed to probe the infrared stimulated luminescence (IRSL) signals from feldspar fractions in the polymineral fine-grains from three of the samples, from archaeological Layers 2, 3 and 4 respectively, which have been dated using fine-grained quartz. The IRSL signals, albeit relatively weak, were observed, so were post-IR IRSL and post-IR OSL signals. This prompted us an opportunity of using feldspar signals for dating the strongly weathered sediments at the site. Both the infrared and post-IR OSL measurements of these samples showed a dominant fast component. The application of the single-aliquot regeneration dose (SAR) protocol to the IRSL and post-IR IRSL signals as well as that of post-IR OSL signals was then made for dating. On the account of the weak IRSL and post-IR IRSL signals apparently due to the strong weathering and on the basis of the dose recovery test, a protocol employing measurement temperatures of 50°C and 270°C was used for the determination of the post-IR IRSL equivalent dose ($pIRIR_{270^\circ C} De$). As the post-IR OSL signals in these samples were intense and decayed fast, an attempt was also made to obtain equivalent doses (post-IR OSL De) for comparison. We obtained the $pIRIR_{270^\circ C} De$ values of 428.8 ± 13.2 Gy, 562.3 ± 18.2 Gy and 694.8 ± 17.9 Gy for the three samples respectively. The corresponding post-IR OSL De values are 345.0 ± 29.4 Gy, 409.6 ± 33.7 Gy and 424.7 ± 32.2 Gy respectively. These De values are all higher than the respective De values of 278.1 ± 3.9 Gy, 330.4 ± 6.0 Gy and 381.2 ± 5.1 Gy published previously for the fine-grained quartz. The corresponding quartz-based OSL ages reported for the three samples were 67.9 ± 2.4 ka, 81.4 ± 3.1 ka and 98.0 ± 3.5 ka respectively. Using our post-IR IRSL signals and assuming minimal effects of the strong weathering on the dose rate calculation based on the previous dating study, the luminescence ages become 89 ± 6 ka, 118 ± 8 ka and 152 ± 9 ka, i.e. about 30-55% (~ 20-55 ka) older. The possibility of age overestimation using the infrared luminescence signals was assessed by the comparison of the De values obtained with different measurement conditions. No evidence of poor bleaching of IRSL and post-IR IRSL signals was found. As most archaeological materials at the Fengshuzui site were found in Layer 3 and upper Layer 4, our results thus date the occurrence of the Acheulean-like stone tools from final part of penultimate glaciation (MIS 6) into the last interglacial (MIS 5e). This is different from the ages within MIS 5 for Layers 3 and 4 at the Fengshuzui site estimated before.

Luminescence and radiocarbon chronology of Holocene fire-Induced geomorphological processes in the Khangai Mountains, Mongolia

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Geomorphological processes are widely reflected in the spatial distribution of aeolian sediments and forest fires in the Khangai Mountains of Mongolia. In this study funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) we aim at reconstructing the landscape evolution by investigating sediment-soil sequences in a variety of relief positions in the Khangai Mountains. In order to understand these processes quantitatively, it is mandatory to set up a reliable chronological framework for the sediments and soils under study, which is carried out by luminescence and radiocarbon dating. The first luminescence measurements yielded deposition ages of 13-11 ka before present (BP) for aeolian sand covering periglacial slope deposits. The radiocarbon ages of charcoal and soil organic matter from the upper soils yielded ages of up to 2 ka BP. Based on our first data set we can distinguish among a period of extensive aeolian transport and sand accumulation during the late glacial period, a period of geomorphological stability during the early and middle Holocene and a period of enhanced aeolian, colluvial and alluvial processes for the past 4.5 ka. During the latter period, the abundance of charcoal evidences a major change in landscape ecology.